

This scientific publication was accepted on 15 January 2023 in the journal Deep-Sea Research Part II. The published version can be accessed in the following link:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0967064523000152>

Patterns in the plankton – spatial distribution and long-term variability of copepods on the Agulhas Bank

Jenny A. Huggett^{a,b,*}, Margaux Noyon^c, Jacob Carstensen^d, David R. Walker^e

^a Oceans and Coastal Research, Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, Private Bag X4390, Cape Town, 8000, South Africa

^b Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Private Bag X3, Rondebosch, 7701, Cape Town, South Africa

^c Department of Oceanography and Institute for Coastal and Marine Research, Nelson Mandela University, Gqeberha, 6001, South Africa

^d Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej 399, PO Box 358, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

^e Department of Conservation and Marine Sciences, Cape Peninsula University of Technology, PO Box 652, Cape Town 8000, South Africa

* Corresponding author.

Email address: jenny.huggett@gmail.com

1 **Patterns in the plankton – spatial distribution and long-term variability of**
2 **copepods on the Agulhas Bank**

3 Jenny A. Huggett^{a,b,*}, Margaux Noyon^c, Jacob Carstensen^d, David R. Walker^e

4 ^a Oceans and Coastal Research, Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment, Private Bag X4390,
5 Cape Town, 8000, South Africa

6 ^b Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, Private Bag X3, Rondebosch, 7701, Cape
7 Town, South Africa

8 ^c Department of Oceanography and Institute for Coastal and Marine Research, Nelson Mandela University,
9 Gqeberha, 6001, South Africa

10 ^d Department of Ecoscience, Aarhus University, Frederiksborgvej 399, PO Box 358, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

11 ^e Department of Conservation and Marine Sciences, Cape Peninsula University of Technology, PO Box 652,
12 Cape Town 8000, South Africa

13

14 * Corresponding author.

15 *Email address:* jenny.huggett@gmail.com

16

17 **Keywords:**

18 *Calanus agulhensis*; Cold ridge; Functional traits; Pelagic ecosystem; Time series; South Africa;
19 Zooplankton

20

21 **Abstract**

22 Copepods dominate the zooplankton community on the broad Agulhas Bank off southern
23 Africa, where they provide an important food resource for pelagic fish and other biota.
24 Previous studies have shown the dominant copepod *Calanus agulhensis*, which may comprise
25 up to 80% of copepod biomass, to be strongly associated with the productive cold ridge of
26 upwelled water on the central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) Agulhas Bank. However, there is
27 little information available on other copepod taxa, and whether the Agulhas Bank community
28 has changed over time in response to environmental variability or other ecosystem changes,
29 such as the recent eastward shift in pelagic fish distribution. We use in situ temperature,
30 chlorophyll *a*, and zooplankton data collected annually in late spring to explore spatio-
31 temporal variability in copepod biomass and species composition on the Agulhas Bank over a
32 24-year period, from 1988-2011. Functional traits were used to interpret the observed
33 patterns. Total copepod abundance and biomass was concentrated on the outer central and
34 eastern shelf (>100 m), coincident with the region of elevated chl *a* at 30 m, and largely
35 downstream from cooler subsurface water linked to the cold ridge and coastal upwelling.
36 Current and cruise-feeding herbivores *C. agulhensis* and the smaller Para- and
37 Clausocalanidae collectively accounted for 73% and 54% of total copepod biomass and
38 abundance respectively, driving the main patterns for total biomass. *C. agulhensis*
39 copepodites showed an ontogenetic shift in distribution with distance offshore and
40 downstream from the cold ridge, and accumulation of older stages near the southern tip of the

41 bank. The upwelling specialist *Calanoides natalis* was closely associated with shelf-edge
42 upwelling, particularly near the Agulhas Bight, but was low in biomass compared to the
43 Benguela upwelling system. The current/cruise-feeding detritivores *Metridia lucens* and the
44 Oncaidae were largely associated with the western sector of the bank but showed different
45 niche preferences. *M. lucens* inhabited the chl-rich outer bank of the western Agulhas Bank
46 (WAB), likely a continuation of the southern Benguela upwelling system community, while
47 oncaeid biomass was associated with deeper thermoclines across the WAB and western part
48 of the CAB that often feature accumulations of the gelatinous zooplankton they feed on.
49 *Centropages* spp. and the Oithonidae, mainly omnivorous ambush feeders, were associated
50 with the inner to mid-shelf region of the WAB and CAB, away from the main influence of
51 the Agulhas Current. *Centropages* biomass aligned well with elevated chl *a* on the inner
52 WAB, likely an extension of the Benguela community (*C. brachiatus*), and with the cold
53 ridge over the inner CAB shelf, matching earlier patterns linked to *C. chierchiae*. Oithonidae
54 were widespread but low in biomass, and scarce over the Agulhas Current-influenced outer
55 shelf, suggesting a suboptimal environment overall for this group compared to the cooler
56 Benguela upwelling region. Current-feeding and omnivorous *Pleuromamma* spp., known to
57 be deep vertical migrators, were concentrated beyond the WAB shelf edge. Total copepod
58 biomass showed a significant decline over the entire Agulhas Bank during the 24-year time
59 series, as did all stages of *C. agulhensis*, including large nauplii, and the small calanoids
60 (Paracalanidae and Clausocalanidae). No long-term trends were observed for the other
61 copepod taxa. We found no trends in temperature, but a significant but weak (1.5% yr⁻¹)
62 increase in chl *a* at 30 m. Although there was no obvious shift in copepod biomass in
63 response to the eastward shift in pelagic fish in ca. 1996, there were significant negative
64 relationships between copepod biomass (for total copepods and *C. agulhensis*) and pelagic
65 fish biomass (total, anchovy and redeye) from 1988-2011, with significantly lower copepod
66 biomass after 1998 compared to before. This suggests predation pressure has an important
67 top-down influence on copepod biomass on the Agulhas Bank. Bottom-up forcing from
68 environmental drivers cannot be ruled out, however, despite ambiguous results from in situ
69 and remote data series, and long-term warming due to climate change is expected to
70 negatively impact ecosystem productivity at the large scale.

71

72 **1. Introduction**

73 Plankton are the foundation of most marine food webs, providing food to higher trophic
74 levels such as fish, seabirds and marine mammals. Copepods, the most abundant metazoans
75 in the ocean (Schminke, 2007), typically dominate the zooplankton in terms of both
76 abundance and biomass and form the intermediate trophic link between phytoplankton and
77 fish. They play a key role in carbon export via the biological pump, and are ideal indicators
78 of climate change, responding rapidly to changes in the environment (Richardson, 2008).

79 Copepods are highly diverse, with over 11 000 known species (Walter and Boxshall, 2020).
80 Copepod diversity on the Agulhas Bank, the triangular-shaped continental shelf off the
81 southern coast of South Africa, was investigated initially by Cleve (1904) and later by De

82 Decker (1973, 1984), who compiled distribution maps for 80 copepod species within the
83 south-eastern Atlantic and south-western Indian Oceans, based on near-surface plankton
84 samples collected during surveys in the 1960s (De Decker, 1984). Diversity over the bank, in
85 particular the central region, was relatively low (≥ 10 -20 species per sample) compared to the
86 Agulhas Current (≥ 30 -40 species). De Decker (1984) suggested the Agulhas Bank was the
87 centre of dispersal for three species - *Calanus agulhensis* (referred to as *Calanus*
88 *finmarchicus s.l.*), *Candacia bipinnata* and *Centropages chierchiae*, although the latter
89 species was much more widely distributed.

90 Regular zooplankton sampling over the Agulhas Bank was initiated in 1988, during annual
91 acoustic surveys in late spring to estimate the biomass of pelagic fish (Peterson et al., 1992).
92 These surveys showed that zooplankton biomass was dominated by a single copepod species,
93 *C. agulhensis*, which comprised between 53 and 82% of total copepod biomass over the
94 entire Agulhas Bank and up to 85% over the eastern Agulhas Bank (Verheye et al., 1994).
95 Subsequent research effort focused on measuring growth and production of *C. agulhensis*
96 (e.g., Peterson et al., 1992; Peterson and Hutchings, 1995; Hutchings et al., 1995), as feeding
97 studies had shown that these large calanoid copepods were a key food source for
98 commercially important small pelagic fish that spawn on the Agulhas Bank, in particular
99 anchovy *Engraulis encrasicolus* (James, 1987; James and Findlay, 1989) and redeye round
100 herring *Etrumeus whiteheadii* (Wallace-Fincham, 1987). Sardine *Sardinops sagax* diet was
101 thought to comprise mainly phytoplankton, but later studies showed that this species was also
102 predominantly zoophagous (van der Lingen, 2002), although feeding on smaller zooplankton
103 prey compared to anchovy.

104 Several studies have noted a quasi-permanent ‘ridge’ of cool upwelled water stretching across
105 the mid-shelf region of the central and eastern Agulhas Bank (Fig. 1), which is thought to
106 have an important influence on productivity over the Bank. The first to describe this feature
107 were Swart and Largier (1987), followed by a more detailed description over several years by
108 Boyd and Shillington (1994). The latter defined the ‘cool-water ridge’ as a subsurface feature
109 showing at a maximum temperature of 17°C within the upper 30 m of the water column,
110 although it was also observed in satellite imagery (Probyn et al., 1994). The ridge seems most
111 prevalent during summer (Hutchings, 1994; Roberts, 2005), when it is associated with
112 subsurface (10-20 m) chlorophyll maxima of $>2 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ (Probyn et al., 1994). Current
113 measurements indicate cyclonic flow of warmer surface water around the cold ridge, when
114 present, with westward flow offshore and eastward flow inshore (Fig. 1; Boyd and
115 Shillington, 1994).

116 Both the forcing mechanism of the ridge and the origin of the cold, nutrient-rich bottom water
117 within it have been a matter of some debate (Walker, 1986; Swart and Largier, 1987; Boyd
118 and Shillington, 1994; Probyn et al., 1994; Roberts, 2005; Lutjeharms, 2006; Chang, 2008;
119 Jackson et al., 2012). Boyd and Shillington (1994) suggested that upwelling of the
120 thermocline is induced by divergent flow due to the widening of the continental shelf
121 between Port Elizabeth (now Gqeberha) and Knysna. Roberts (1995) suggested the cold ridge
122 may simply be a mesoscale upwelling filament that forms due to intensive (and extensive)
123 wind-driven coastal upwelling off the Knysna-Tsitsikamma coast (~ 23 - 25°E), with current-

124 driven advection of the plume resulting in the extension of the feature southwestwards across
125 the mid-shelf region. Suggested origins of the cold shelf bottom water that forms the cold
126 ridge include westward transport of South Indian Central Water that upwells off Port Alfred
127 (Swart and Largier, 1987; Lutjeharms, 2006), and shelf-edge upwelling along the whole
128 southeastern edge of the Agulhas Bank (Jackson et al., 2012). As Jackson et al. (2012)
129 conclude, there may be more than one source of the cold bottom water, and more than one
130 mechanism for the cool ridge.

131 Peterson et al. (1992) observed highest densities of *C. agulhensis* copepods on the central to
132 eastern Agulhas Bank, with greatest biomass associated with the cold ridge south of Mossel
133 Bay, and low biomass on the western Agulhas Bank. This distribution pattern was ascribed to
134 higher chlorophyll *a* concentration, which would enhance growth rates, as well as localised
135 retention of copepods due to the semi-closed, cyclonic circulation around the ridge (Peterson
136 et al. 1992). All stages of *C. agulhensis* were largely centred over the cyclonic feature,
137 although there was some evidence of westward advection of older stages, and a westward
138 displacement of biomass in November 1990 when the ridge was absent (Largier et al., 1992;
139 Peterson and Hutchings, 1995; Hutchings et al., 1995). The retentive nature of the ridge was
140 confirmed by Huggett (2003), using a 13-year time series, which showed a progressive
141 westward ontogenetic shift in distribution across the Bank in years when the ridge was
142 absent.

143 More than two decades have passed since the last review of copepod distribution and
144 community structure on the Agulhas Bank (Verheye et al., 1994), while various aspects of *C.*
145 *agulhensis* ecology, including feeding preferences, growth and development, production and
146 vertical migratory behaviour were reviewed by Huggett and Richardson (2000). While much
147 is now known about *C. agulhensis*, there is scant information on the other copepod taxa that
148 contribute to the Agulhas Bank community, including their distribution and abundance, and
149 whether these have changed over time. Several studies have highlighted marked
150 environmental or ecosystem changes on the Agulhas Bank over the past few decades,
151 including the so-called ‘eastward shift’ of pelagic fish in 1996, with severe implications for
152 top predators such as seabirds (Roy et al., 2007; Coetzee et al., 2008b; Crawford et al. 2008;
153 Blamey et al. 2015; Crawford et al., 2016; van der Lingen and Hampton, 2018). The question
154 of whether there have been parallel changes in the lower trophic levels, in particular the
155 zooplankton community, remains to be addressed.

156 A recent approach for exploring patterns in zooplankton distribution in various habitats is the
157 functional trait approach. Functional traits are phenotypic characteristics that impact fitness
158 and are relevant to ecosystem function (Violle et al., 2007). They can be characterized
159 according to their type, such as morphological, physiological, behavioural and life history, as
160 well as their ecological function, such as feeding, growth/reproduction and survival
161 (Litchman et al., 2013). Characterizing zooplankton traits and trade-offs can enhance
162 understanding of selection pressures and diversity patterns that emerge in different
163 ecosystems along major environmental gradients, as well as the potential response of species
164 to current and future climate-mediated changes in the ocean (Litchman et al. 2013; Benedetti
165 et al., 2018).

166 Recent efforts to compile functional traits for a wide number of copepod species from
167 different ocean regions include those by Benedetti (2015), Benedetti et al. (2016, 2022), Brun
168 et al. (2016, 2017) and Becker et al. (2021). Key traits selected include trophic group
169 (herbivorous, carnivorous, omnivorous, etc.; Becker et al., 2021), feeding strategy (active
170 ambush feeding, current feeding, filter feeding, etc.; Kiørboe, 2011), egg-spawning strategy
171 (broadcast- or sac-spawner), and myelination of the nervous system (a taxon-specific survival
172 feature confined to calanoid copepods, enabling faster reactions to predatory attacks; Lenz et
173 al., 2000; Lenz, 2012). Body size is considered a master trait due to its influence on other
174 traits such as feeding, growth rate and diel vertical migration (Kiørboe and Hirst, 2014;
175 Ohman and Romagnan, 2016; McGinty et al., 2018).

176 In this paper we use a 24-year time series to explore spatial and temporal variability in the
177 dominant copepod taxa on the Agulhas Bank during austral spring between 1988 and 2011,
178 posing several key questions: (1) what are the dominant copepod taxa on the Agulhas Bank
179 and do they display distinct spatial patterns related to environmental variables; (2) what are
180 the long-term patterns or trends in copepod biomass and taxonomic composition on the
181 Agulhas Bank; and (3) what are the implications of the observed copepod patterns, in
182 particular of *C. agulhensis*, for future ecosystem functioning on the Agulhas Bank? We use
183 functional traits as a framework to guide interpretation of the patterns observed in copepod
184 distribution on the Agulhas Bank, and also explore relationships between copepod and
185 pelagic fish biomass for a perspective on potential top-down predation.

186

187 **2. Material and methods**

188 *2.1 Sampling*

189 Sampling was conducted on the Agulhas Bank, off the south coast of South Africa, during
190 annual hydro-acoustic stock-assessment surveys of pelagic fish in late spring (late October to
191 early December) between 1988 and 2011 (Fig. S1). This time of the year coincides with the
192 main spawning period of anchovy and sardine (van der Lingen and Huggett, 2003). Surveys
193 took place on either the FRS *Africana* or the RV *Algoa*. Station positions varied between
194 cruises (see Fig. S2 for zooplankton sampling locations during each survey) due to the
195 stratified random survey design (Coetzee et al., 2008a). In this study, the Agulhas Bank was
196 sub-divided into three regions characterised by different hydrological conditions (Probyn et
197 al., 1994), the western, central and eastern Agulhas Bank (WAB, CAB, and EAB
198 respectively, Fig. 1).

199 Temperature in the upper 200 m was acquired from several sources over the time series,
200 including underwater temperature sensors attached to a rosette water sampler (used at 10 nm
201 intervals along transects where zooplankton sampling was conducted from 1988 to 2001) and
202 a California Vertical Egg Tow (CalVET) net (used at 5 nm intervals along all transects), and
203 Seabird CTD samplers (from 2002-2011). Salinity data were not available for the first half of
204 the time-series (prior to 2002) so are not considered here, as temporal trends cannot be
205 assessed reliably using only 10 years of data.

206 Vertical profiles of chlorophyll *a* (chl *a*) concentration in the upper 200 m were obtained
207 during both day and night using *in situ* fluorescence measured with a Chelsea Aquatracka
208 MkIII from 1988 to 2001, which was subsequently replaced by a WETLAB fluorometer.
209 Fluorescence profiles were calibrated using extracted chl *a* concentration measured at a
210 number of depths per station (Mitchell-Innes et al., 1999). Quenching may occur on the bank
211 but was not taken into account in the analysis in this study. Instrumentation errors in 1999
212 and 2001 resulted in insufficient chl *a* data being available for those years, so they were
213 excluded from the chl *a* analysis.

214 Zooplankton samples were collected from the upper 200 m, or down to 5 to 10 m from the
215 bottom at shallower stations using a vertically hauled Bongo net (0.57 m diameter, 200- μ m
216 mesh) equipped with a General Oceanics flowmeter. Samples were preserved in 5% buffered
217 formalin. In the laboratory, copepods from subsamples (two times 2 mL) were counted and
218 identified microscopically to stage, species or taxonomic category as described in Huggett et
219 al. (2009). The following categories were enumerated in this study: Calanoida: C1, C2, C3,
220 C4, C5, male and female stages of *Calanoides natalis* and *Calanus agulhensis*; juvenile, male
221 and female stages of *Centropages* spp., *Metridia lucens*, *Pleuromamma* spp. and *Rhincalanus*
222 spp.; large calanoid nauplii, small calanoids (Paracalanidae and Clausocalanidae), other large
223 calanoids (e.g., Aetideidae, Candaciidae, Eucalanidae, Euchaetidae, Lucicutiidae,
224 *Nannocalanus minor*); Cyclopoida: Oithonidae, Corycaeidae, Oncaeidae, other cyclopoids
225 (e.g., Sapphirinidae); and Harpacticoida. For the years 1989 to 1992, stages C1 to C3 of *C.*
226 *agulhensis* and *C. natalis* were not enumerated separately but were pooled as "juveniles".
227 Typical counts ranged from 42 to 3551 individuals per subsample (mean = 398 for 5 cruises
228 considered randomly over the times series), and most counts were made by the same 3 or 4
229 analysts over the time series, with occasional checks to ensure identifications were consistent
230 and comparable.

231 Integrated copepod abundance (no m^{-2}) at each station (see Figs. S1 and S2) was calculated
232 by multiplying copepod density (no m^{-3}) by the sampling depth (m). Copepod biomass (mg
233 dry weight m^{-2}) was calculated by multiplying the abundance (no m^{-2}) of each taxonomic
234 category and copepodite stage listed above by the mean dry weight of an individual animal
235 (Huggett et al., 2009; see their Table 1). Biomasses of all stages per species or genus (e.g., *C.*
236 *agulhensis*, *C. natalis*, *Centropages* spp., *Metridia lucens*, *Pleuromamma* spp. and
237 *Rhincalanus* spp.) were summed to obtain a total biomass per category at each station
238 sampled. Biomass in terms of carbon (mg C m^{-2}) was calculated assuming carbon was 40% of
239 dry weight, after Peterson et al. (1990).

240 2.2 Statistical analysis of spatial distributions

241 Copepod, temperature and chl *a* data were distributed irregularly over the study area among
242 years; consequently, their spatio-temporal variability had to be accounted for in order to
243 produce comparable results. We calculated the spatial distribution for all response variables
244 (copepod abundance and biomass, temperature, depth of 17°C and chl *a*) for each year using
245 a two-step procedure, consisting of a Generalized Additive Model (GAM) to produce the
246 mean spatial distribution across all years, and an Ordinary Kriging (OK) analysis of residuals

247 from this analysis to produce spatial distributions for individual years. These analyses were
 248 carried out in SAS v. 9.3 using PROC GAM and PROC KRIGE2D.

249 All analyses were based on discrete observations of the response variables ($z(x_i, y_i, t_i)$, $i =$
 250 $1, \dots, n$) from different sampling locations ((x_i, y_i)) and years ((t_i)), i.e. location and year were
 251 predictor variables. Surface (0-10 m), subsurface (30 m) and integrated (0-100 m for chl a ,
 252 and 0-200 m for copepods) values were compiled from the depth profiles for the location
 253 (x_i, y_i) . Chlorophyll a and all copepod variables were normalized by log-transformation
 254 before modelling the spatio-temporal variations and results were back-transformed after the
 255 analysis.

256 First, we used a 2-dimensional spline ($s(x, y)$; a smoothing function that is part of GAM)
 257 to describe the mean spatial distribution across all years, allowing for systematic change in
 258 mean level among years through a parametric factor ($year_t$)

$$259 \quad z(x, y, t) = s(x, y) + year_t + r(x, y, t)$$

260 The residuals ($r(x, y, t)$) from the GAM were analysed with OK for each year separately,
 261 using a spherical model fitted on the empirical variograms for all years combined to describe
 262 the spatial correlation as function of distance (Cressie 1993). The spatial distribution of
 263 the GAM residuals predicted with OK described spatial deviations from the overall mean
 264 spatial distribution ($s(x, y)$) for each year separately, i.e., for a given year ($t = t_j$) the
 265 residuals from the GAM were modelled with the OK predictor ($\hat{r}(x, y, t_j)$) based on
 266 observations from that given year and the common spherical variogram model

$$267 \quad r(x, y, t_j) = \hat{r}(x, y, t_j) + e(x, y, t_j)$$

268 where $e(x, y, t_j)$ describe the residuals from the OK analysis. Consequently, the estimated
 269 spatial distribution in a given year is

$$270 \quad \hat{z}(x, y, t_j) = \hat{s}(x, y) + \widehat{year}_j + \hat{r}(x, y, t_j)$$

271 and the estimated spatial distribution across all years (n_{year} is the total number of years) is

$$272 \quad \hat{z}(x, y) = \hat{s}(x, y) + \frac{1}{n_{year}} \cdot \sum_j \widehat{year}_j + \frac{1}{n_{year}} \cdot \sum_j \hat{r}(x, y, t_j)$$

273 Trends in annual means of spatially
 274 integrated copepod, temperature and chl a variables were investigated by averaging, for each
 275 year separately, $\hat{z}(x, y, t_j)$ over the entire study area as well as the three subregions
 276 separately (Fig. 1). Furthermore, the geographical location of areas with high copepod
 277 biomass (for species, stages and entire community) was found by calculating a center of
 278 gravity (CoG) as the average coordinates of grid cells exceeding the 90th percentile of the
 279 entire spatial distribution. All spatial distributions and trends of the response variables
 presented below resulted from the combined analysis of GAM and OK.

280

281 2.3 Functional trait analysis

282 The dominant copepod taxa were allocated to one of eleven functional groups, as defined by
283 Benedetti et al. (2022), based on five species-level functional traits: body size (mean
284 maximum body size), trophic group (omnivore–herbivore, omnivore–carnivore, omnivore–
285 detritivore, strict carnivore and omnivore), feeding mode (ambush feeding, current feeding,
286 cruise feeding, particle feeding, current–cruise feeding and current–ambush feeding),
287 myelination (myelinated or non-myelinated) and spawning mode (free-spawning or sac-
288 spawning). Diel vertical migratory behaviour (DVM) was not considered as a defining trait as
289 it tends to be very ‘plastic’ for most species, varying according to the environmental
290 conditions (e.g., light or food availability), predation risk and the species’ ontogeny, i.e.,
291 developmental stage (Benedetti et al. 2015).

292 The functional groups defined by Benedetti et al. (2022) were as follows: FG1 (myelinated
293 cruise-feeding omnivores–herbivores), FG2 (amyelinated cruise-feeding detritivores), FG3
294 (myelinated mixed-feeding or cruise-feeding detritivores), FG4 (amyelinated ambush-feeding
295 carnivores), FG5 (current-or cruise-feeding carnivores), FG6 (myelinated current-feeding
296 omnivores–herbivores), FG7 (myelinated current-feeding omnivores–herbivores), FG8
297 (amyelinated ambush-or current-feeding carnivores), FG9 (amyelinated current-feeding
298 omnivores), FG10 (amyelinated ambush-feeding omnivores), FG11 (amyelinated mixed-
299 feeding omnivores).

300 Functional traits of the dominant taxa on the Agulhas Bank were defined using size data from
301 Razouls et al. (2005-2022), and other features from Becker et al. (2021) and Benedetti et al.
302 (2022). Additional information used to define functional traits for *C. natalis* and *C. agulhensis*
303 was sourced from local studies by Verheye and Field (1992), Huggett and Richardson (2000)
304 and Huggett et al. (2007).

305 2.4 Other analyses

306 Long-term trends in the environmental variables (mean annual temperature at the surface and
307 at a depth of 30 m, mean annual depth of the 17°C isotherm, mean annual chl a concentration
308 at the surface and at a depth of 30 m, mean annual integrated chl a concentration within the
309 upper 100 m) were investigated using linear regression analysis. Linear regression analysis
310 and correlation analysis respectively were used to explore trends in, and relationships
311 between, the area and volume of upwelled water (defined as water colder than 17°C within
312 the upper 30 m) in the coastal zone (defined here as bottom depths shallower than 50 m) as
313 well as for the cold ridge (defined here as bottom depths between 50 and 200 m) on the CAB
314 and EAB. Long-term trends in biomass of each dominant copepod species or taxonomic
315 category, as well as of each developmental stage of *C. agulhensis* (from nauplii to adults),
316 were investigated using both linear and non-linear (exponential) functions. Where linear
317 regressions were found to be significant, exponential fits invariably yielded similar or greater
318 r^2 values, thus were considered preferable for display.

319 To obtain a synoptic view of the spatial and temporal species composition on the Agulhas
320 Bank, we applied a non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (nMDS; metaMDS function of the
321 vegan r package) to the biomass of each copepod species for each area (EAB, CAB and
322 WAB) and for each year. The nMDS was performed on a Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrix for
323 which the data were square-root transformed and standardised with a Wisconsin double
324 standardisation (Oksanen et al., 2020).

325 For a perspective on possible predation pressure on Agulhas Bank copepods, linear
326 regression analysis was used to investigate relationships between annual acoustic estimates of
327 pelagic fish biomass (anchovy *Engraulis encrasicolus*, sardine *Sardinops sagax* and redeye
328 round herring *Etrumeus whiteheadi*, and total pelagic fish biomass) during the November
329 surveys (Coetzee et al., 2008a; DAFF, 2018) and annual total copepod biomass estimates
330 from the GAM.

331

332 **3. Results**

333 *3.1 Spatial variability in environmental conditions*

334 Mean sea surface temperature (temperature at 5 m, SST) over the Agulhas Bank during late
335 spring (late October to early December) from 1988 to 2011 was 18.8°C (Table 1), with
336 warmest temperatures (20-22°C) along the outer central and eastern shelf due to the influence
337 of the Agulhas Current (Fig. 2a). Cooler water (<17°C) was found inshore (<100 m) over the
338 WAB and in pockets between Mossel Bay and Port Alfred on the EAB.

339 At a depth of 30 m, cool (<17°C) water was present over most of the EAB on average (Fig.
340 2b), extending westwards from Port Alfred over the entire inner shelf (<100 m) and much of
341 the outer shelf (100-200 m) as far as Mossel Bay. South of Mossel Bay, a tongue of cool
342 water curved offshore along the 100 m isobath towards the centre of the bank, coincident
343 with past in situ observations of the cold ridge (Swart and Largier, 1987; Boyd and
344 Shillington, 1994; Roberts 2005). A secondary tongue of cooler water was evident further
345 offshore over the 200 m isobath, in the vicinity of the Agulhas Bight (the sharp change in
346 continental shelf edge orientation at ~23°E). Mean temperatures over the central and
347 southernmost part of the bank at 30 m were considerably warmer, particularly along the
348 shelf-edge. Warm water (>18°C) also extended across the outer WAB at 30 m, but mean
349 temperatures over the inshore region of the WAB (<100 m) were much cooler (<16°C), as
350 expected due to episodic upwelling-favourable winds during summer (see review by Largier
351 et al., 1992).

352 The difference in temperature between the surface and a depth of 30 m (Fig. 2c) highlights
353 the strong contrast in the upper water column characteristics between the western and eastern
354 sectors of the bank, with an average difference of just 1°C in the west (apart from the inshore
355 area of the WAB) compared to 2-3°C in the east. The depth of the 17°C isotherm was below
356 40 m on average over the WAB and much of the CAB, compared to a relatively shallow
357 mean depth of 28 m for the EAB (Table 1), illustrating the westward deepening of the mixed

358 layer depth across the Bank, as observed in other studies (Largier and Swart, 1987; Probyn et
359 al., 1994; Jackson et al., 2012; Poulton et al., this issue).

360 Mean surface chl *a* over the entire bank was $\sim 1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$ (Table 1). Concentrations were
361 generally elevated ($>1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) over the EAB (Fig. 2d) as well as inshore on the WAB due to
362 upwelling, with highest concentrations ($>3 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) in the vicinity of Port Alfred. Chl *a* was
363 lowest ($<0.5 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) over the inner shelf ($<100 \text{ m}$) of the CAB and also relatively low ($0.5\text{-}1$
364 mg m^{-3}) over the outer shelf region ($100\text{-}200 \text{ m}$) of the WAB and much of the CAB.

365 At a depth of 30 m, there was a broad band of elevated chl *a* ($>1 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) that followed the
366 bathymetry of the outer shelf ($100\text{-}200 \text{ m}$), extending westwards from $\sim 25^\circ\text{E}$ over the entire
367 outer bank towards Cape Town (Fig. 2e). An area of elevated chl *a* was also evident between
368 Port Elizabeth and Port Alfred, particularly along the edge of the continental shelf. Chl *a* was
369 much lower over the shallow ($<100 \text{ m}$) triangular section of the bank between Cape Agulhas
370 and Mossel Bay, as well as along parts of the shelf edge west of the Agulhas Bight.

371 The distribution of integrated chl *a* within the upper 100 m followed a similar pattern to that
372 of chl *a* at 30 m. Integrated chl *a* was elevated ($>50 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$) over much of the outer shelf, as
373 well as inshore on the WAB, and was highest ($>70 \text{ mg m}^{-2}$) over the entire eastern shelf
374 region between Port Elizabeth and Port Alfred (Fig. 2f).

375 *3.2 Spatial variability in copepod abundance, biomass and composition*

376 Mean copepod abundance over the Agulhas Bank during late spring was concentrated over
377 the mid- to outer shelf of the Agulhas Bank, aligned with the 100 m isobath on the EAB,
378 shifting further offshore west of Mossel Bay towards the southern tip of the Bank, then along
379 the outer WAB (Fig. 3a). Abundance was greatest ($>160\,000 \text{ m}^{-2}$) between 20 and 24°E , but
380 relatively low ($<80\,000 \text{ m}^{-2}$) over the inner shelf ($<100 \text{ m}$) between Cape Town and Mossel
381 Bay, in the Bight region, and on the outer shelf east of 24°E . Mean copepod biomass
382 displayed a similar pattern (Fig. 3b) but was most concentrated ($>1000 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$) beyond the
383 100 m isobath. Peak biomass ($>1400 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$) was located near the southern tip of the
384 CAB, with a secondary centre of high biomass south of Plettenberg Bay, north of the Bight.
385 Biomass was relatively low ($<800 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$) over the entire inner shelf. Areas of greatest
386 copepod abundance and biomass overlapped broadly with the region of elevated chl *a* at 30 m
387 depth, as delineated by the 0.9 mg m^{-3} contour (Figs. 3a, b).

388 Eight species or taxonomic groups of copepods are reported on in detail below, which along
389 with large calanoid nauplii (see section 3.3) collectively comprised 98% of total copepod
390 abundance and 94% of total copepod biomass (see Table 2). “Other copepod taxa” comprised
391 the balance. The large ($\sim 3 \text{ mm}$ total length) calanoid *C. agulhensis* and small ($\sim 1 \text{ mm}$)
392 calanoids from the families Paracalanidae and Clausocalanidae together comprised 73% of
393 the biomass and 54% of abundance (Table 2), while large calanoid nauplii contributed a
394 further 10% to total abundance. The Oithonidae comprised $<1\%$ of total copepod biomass,
395 but 18% of total abundance. Other copepod taxa commonly found, but which comprised $<2\%$
396 of both abundance and biomass, included the calanoid families Acartiidae, Candaciidae,

397 Eucalanidae, Euchaetidae, Lucicutiidae and Rhincalanidae, the cyclopoid families
398 Corycaeidae and Sapphirinidae, and harpacticoid copepods. Functional traits for the eight
399 dominant taxa described below, as well as their allocation to functional groups as per
400 Benedetti et al. (2022), are listed in Table 3.

401 Distribution patterns of the dominant copepod taxa showed some interesting variations.
402 *Calanus agulhensis* (small to medium-sized myelinated current-feeding herbivores, Table 3),
403 comprised 50% of total copepod biomass and ranked third overall in abundance (Table 2).
404 This species was commonly found across the entire Agulhas Bank (Fig. S3), but mean
405 biomass over the time series was distributed similarly to that of total copepod biomass, with
406 peak biomass ($>800 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$) near the southern tip of the bank and a secondary peak on the
407 outer shelf south of Plettenberg Bay (Fig. 4a). Biomass was consistently low ($<100 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$)
408 over the inner WAB (Fig. S2). The small calanoid copepods (Para- and Clausocalanidae,
409 small to medium-sized myelinated current feeders, Table 3) were the most abundant group
410 overall (37% of total abundance, Table 2), and the second most important group in terms of
411 biomass (23% total biomass). Their distribution was widespread over the entire bank (Fig.
412 S4), with mean biomass showing a similar pattern to that for total copepod biomass but
413 extending further east (Fig. 4b). Although both abundant and ubiquitous, the regions of
414 greatest mean biomass of this group generally corresponded to areas of elevated mean chl *a*
415 ($>0.9 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) at a depth of 30 m.

416 Biomass of *Metridia lucens* (myelinated current/cruise-feeding detritivores, Table 3), a
417 medium-large species capable of diel vertical migration between the epipelagic and
418 mesopelagic layers (Longhurst and Williams, 1979), was consistently concentrated over the
419 outer shelf of the WAB west of $\sim 21^\circ\text{E}$ (Figs. S5, 4c), with low biomass elsewhere on the
420 Bank, yet still ranked third in terms of total biomass. The two nodes of peak biomass also
421 overlapped with areas of higher mean chl *a* ($>0.9 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) at a depth of 30 m. The upwelling-
422 associated species *Calanoides natalis* (Peterson, 1998; Bradford-Grieve et al., 2017; small to
423 medium-sized myelinated current-feeding herbivores, Table 3), similar in size to *C.*
424 *agulhensis*, was mostly restricted to the outer shelf and shelf edge of the eastern and central
425 Agulhas Bank, but also occurred along the shelf edge of the WAB (Fig. S6). Greatest mean
426 biomass, an order of magnitude lower than that of *C. agulhensis*, was centred around the cool
427 (at 30 m depth, Fig. 2a) Agulhas Bight ($>40 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$), with a secondary peak at the extreme
428 southern tip of the bank (Fig. 4d).

429 Biomass distribution of *Centropages* spp. (amyelinated current-ambush-feeding
430 omnivores/herbivores, Table 3) was spatially consistent for much of the time series (Fig. S7).
431 On average, biomass was most concentrated over the inner to mid-shelf regions of the WAB
432 and the eastern part of the CAB (Fig. 4e), with low biomass in deeper water and east of
433 Plettenberg Bay. Areas of consistently high biomass on the inner WAB and over the cool
434 ridge were characterised by both higher mean chl *a* ($>0.9 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) and cooler mean
435 temperatures ($<17^\circ\text{C}$) at a depth of 30 m. The cyclopoid family Oncaeidae (amyelinated
436 cruise-feeding detritivores, Table 3), was quite widely distributed over the bank (Fig. S8) but
437 mean biomass, which was very high in 1995, was strongly concentrated over the western

438 region, with a sharp decline biomass east of $\sim 21^\circ\text{E}$ (Fig. 4f). This part of the bank is
439 characterised by a deeper mixed layer (Probyn et al., 1994), with warmer water at a depth of
440 30 m compared to the region east of 21°E (Fig. 2b, c). Biomass was markedly lower in the
441 cooler, coastal upwelling-influenced region of the WAB, increasing offshore of the 17°C
442 isotherm at 30 m.

443 The large-sized and strong epi-mesopelagic vertical migrants *Pleuromamma* spp. (Benedetti
444 et al., 2015) were tightly concentrated over the outer shelf region and often beyond for the
445 entire Agulhas Bank (Fig. S9). Their biomass was low overall, but greatest over the outer
446 WAB ($15\text{-}25\text{ mg C m}^{-2}$), and negligible over the inner bank, suggesting a strong positive
447 association with depth (Fig. 4g). At the opposite end of the size spectrum, the tiny ($<1\text{ mm}$)
448 Oithonidae (amyelinated ambush-feeding omnivores, Table 3) were the second-most abundant
449 taxon, but comprised $<1\%$ of total biomass, although many would have been too small to be
450 retained by the $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ -mesh Bongo net (Gallienne and Robins, 2001). This cyclopid group
451 was widely distributed over the bank, with particularly high biomass in 1995 and 1996 (Fig.
452 S10). In most years, biomass was concentrated within the 100 m isobath on the EAB and for
453 much of the CAB but extended over the outer shelf ($>100\text{ m}$) and beyond the shelf edge on
454 the WAB (Fig. 4h). There were no clear associations with cooler temperature or elevated chl
455 *a* concentration, but biomass was consistently low over the warmer outer CAB and EAB
456 where the influence of the Agulhas Current is greatest.

457 The spatial distribution of annual centres of gravity (CoGs, centres of the upper 10% of
458 highest biomass values) for the dominant taxa (Fig. 5a) showed lowest variability (tightest
459 clustering) over the time series for *Pleuromamma* spp., with a node of high biomass on the
460 WAB shelf edge. CoGs for *M. lucens* were also closely grouped along the mid-to outer shelf
461 of the WAB. CoGs for the other species were more broadly distributed, indicating greater
462 interannual variability in the location of peak biomass. *C. agulhensis* CoGs were concentrated
463 on the outer shelf of the CAB, within the region of elevated chl *a* at 30 m, whereas the small
464 calanoid CoGs were mainly clustered over the central CAB. *C. natalis* CoGs were mainly
465 associated with the shelf edge, particularly along the western edge of the Bight. Oncaeid
466 CoGs frequently overlapped those of *M. lucens* on the WAB, with the remainder slightly
467 farther east. *Centropages* spp. CoGs were largely located within the 100 m isobath, most
468 commonly on the CAB. Oithonid CoGs were most concentrated on the inner CAB,
469 overlapping those of *Centropages* spp. and small calanoids (Para- and Clausocalanidae), but
470 with a secondary cluster on the WAB outer shelf.

471 3.3 Spatial variability in biomass of *Calanus agulhensis* stages

472 Mean biomass distribution of large calanoid copepod nauplii as well as of each copepodite
473 stage of *C. agulhensis* is shown in Fig. 6. The nauplii were assumed to be predominantly
474 those of *C. agulhensis*, as (1) this was the most abundant large copepod species, (2) the
475 distribution of the nauplii closely matched the distribution of total *C. agulhensis* biomass and
476 in particular that of the early copepodite stages, and (3) nauplii of the Paracalanidae and
477 Clausocalanidae, whose adults showed a similar distribution to that of *C. agulhensis* (Fig. 4),
478 would have been too small to be retained by a $200\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ -mesh net. Nauplius biomass was

479 concentrated over the 100 m isobath on the EAB and CAB (Fig 6a), extending further
480 offshore south of Mossel Bay, similar to the pattern for total copepod abundance (Fig 3a).
481 There was a secondary “hotspot” near the southern tip of the bank, with moderate biomass
482 extending north-westwards over the outer WAB. Peak biomass was within the region of
483 elevated mean subsurface chl *a*, and also overlapped with the cold ridge.

484

485 Copepodite stages C1-C3 followed a similar pattern to the nauplii (Figs. 6b-d), gradually
486 separating into discrete patches of elevated biomass, including one at the southwestern tip of
487 the bank which became more concentrated with increasing developmental (ontogenetic)
488 stage, and another extending over the outer WAB. Again, peak biomass was distributed
489 within the region of elevated mean subsurface chl *a* and showed partial overlap with the cold
490 ridge. Biomass of C4 copepodites was distributed between three main nodes over the CAB
491 and EAB, with one south of Plettenberg Bay, a second southwest of Mossel Bay, and the
492 third at the southwestern tip of the bank (Fig. 6e). For stage C5 copepodites, the areas of high
493 biomass had resolved into two main nodes (Fig 6f), one south of Plettenberg Bay (EAB) and
494 the second major node at the southern tip of the Agulhas Bank (CAB), but with an area of
495 low biomass still extending along the outer WAB. This pattern was even stronger for female
496 *C. agulhensis* with greatest biomass at the southern tip of the bank (Fig. 6g), whereas for
497 male *C. agulhensis*, which were much less abundant than females, the primary biomass node
498 was a broad area on the outer shelf south of Plettenberg Bay near the Agulhas Bight, with a
499 secondary node at the southern tip of the Agulhas Bank (Fig. 6h).

500

501 Spatial distribution of annual CoGs for the copepodite stages of *C. agulhensis* revealed a
502 gradual shift in peak biomass further offshore and south-westwards with increasing
503 ontogenetic stage (Fig. 5b). Large calanoid nauplii and the youngest copepodite stages (C1-
504 C2) were concentrated just beyond the 100 m isobath, with copepodite stages C3 and C4
505 slightly further offshore, and the older stage C5 copepodites and females the farthest offshore
506 and extending further westward compared to the younger stages. The male CoGs were mainly
507 clustered close to the Agulhas Bight or slightly downstream.

508 *3.4 Interannual variability in environmental conditions*

509 Environmental parameters measured during each cruise are merely snapshots from each year
510 but provide useful context for interpreting patterns in the biota and can also be used to
511 explore long-term trends for this time of year (late spring). Annual estimates of mean SST
512 and temperature at 30 m during late spring for the entire bank showed similar fluctuations
513 over the time series but no significant long-term trends overall (Fig. 7a). Mean temperatures
514 were relatively cool (18.0 and 16.2 °C respectively) at the beginning of the time series,
515 increasing gradually until 1992, after which there was greater interannual variability. There
516 was a sharp decline in mean temperature at both the surface and at 30 m in 1996, followed by
517 warmer temperatures the following year. Mean temperatures were warmest in 2004 (21°C at
518 5 m; 18.5°C at 30 m), after which they gradually declined to the coldest mean values
519 recorded over the time series in 2009 (17.2 at 5 m; 15.9°C at 30 m). The cold peaks in 1996
520 and 2009 were evident for all areas on the bank, as was the warm peak in 2004 (Fig. S11a).

521
522 The depth of the 17°C isotherm, an indicator of the cold ridge when present in the upper 30 m
523 over the CAB and EAB (Boyd and Shillington, 1994), showed similar fluctuations to those in
524 the temperature at 30 m over much of the time series (Fig. 7a), although less so between 2002
525 and 2007. The mean depth of the 17°C isotherm was shallowest overall (<30 m) in 1996 and
526 2009, and deepest (>50 m) in 1997 and 2005. Interannual variability in the 30 m temperature,
527 the difference between SST and the temperature at 30 m, and the depth of the 17°C isotherm,
528 showed similar patterns between regions over most of the time series (Figs. S11b, c, d).

529
530 The area and volume of cool water (<17°C) in the upper 30 m over the CAB and EAB,
531 calculated for depths of the 17°C isotherm shallower than 30 m, during each survey was
532 apportioned between the coastal upwelling region (defined here as within the 50 m isobath)
533 and the region farther offshore that may be considered to represent the cold ridge (defined
534 here as situated between the 50 m and 200 m isobaths; Fig. 7b). The variability and amount
535 of upwelling contributed by the cold ridge was several orders of magnitude greater than that
536 of the coastal upwelling, but all four indices were significantly correlated ($r = 0.8$ to 0.94 , $p <$
537 0.05), suggesting that the coastal and cold ridge upwelling could be considered as one
538 coherent phenomenon. No significant trend in any of these indices was evident over the time
539 series, but they showed high interannual variability at the time of the surveys (Fig. 7b).

540
541 Annual distribution maps of the temperature at 30 m (Fig. 8) show that the cold ridge (which
542 here includes the adjacent coastal upwelled water) was present to a greater or lesser extent
543 during most cruises. It appeared to be most intense during 1988, 1989, 2008 and 2009, when
544 mean temperature at 30 m was below 15°C on the EAB (Fig. S11b), and was most extensive
545 in 2009, when mean temperature at 30 m on the CAB was the coldest over the time series
546 (16.5°C; Fig. S11b). Along with 1996, these four years exhibited the greatest volume of ‘cold
547 ridge upwelled water’ over the bank (>800 km³; Fig. 7b), while 1988 and 2009 had the
548 greatest area of ‘cold ridge upwelled water’ (>30 000 km²). The cold ridge was absent or
549 greatly reduced during 1992, 1997 and 2004 (Fig. 8), when the mean temperature at 30 m on
550 the EAB was close to 18°C (Fig. S11b), and both the area and volume of cold ridge upwelled
551 water were minimal (Fig. 7b).

552
553 Mean chl *a* concentration for the entire Agulhas Bank was typically close to 1 mg m⁻³ at both
554 the surface and at 30 m depth, although concentrations at 30 m were substantially higher than
555 at the surface between 2004 and 2007 (Fig. 7c). Mean surface chl *a* was greatest for the EAB
556 overall (1.27 mg m⁻³; Table 1), with peaks in 1988, 1998, 2008 and 2010 (Fig. S12a), and
557 was lowest over the CAB (0.79). There was a significant long-term increase in mean chl *a* at
558 30 m for the Agulhas Bank as a whole as well as for the CAB ($r^2 = 0.25$ and 0.22 ,
559 respectively, $p < 0.05$). Mean integrated chl *a* was similar in all areas (49-55 mg C m⁻²; Table
560 1) but temporal variability was most in synchrony for the CAB and EAB, where values
561 peaked in 1998 (Figs. S12c and S13).

562

563 *3.5 Interannual variability in copepod biomass and composition*

564 Interannual variability in copepod biomass was generally consistent across all areas of the
565 Agulhas Bank (Fig. 9). The most marked exception was in 1988 when biomass was
566 exceptionally high on the CAB and EAB ($>3000 \text{ mg C m}^{-2}$) compared to the WAB (1200 mg
567 C m^{-2}). Mean copepod biomass on the Agulhas Bank declined significantly over the 24-year
568 times series ($r^2 = 0.52$ exponential fit; $p < 0.001$), including when the 1988 data were excluded
569 ($r^2 = 0.46$ exponential fit; $p < 0.001$). There were significant long-term declines in total
570 biomass for all three regions of the bank, but the decline was most marked for the CAB ($r^2 =$
571 0.44 ; $p < 0.001$). This decline is evident in annual maps of total copepod biomass (Fig. 10),
572 which show mostly lower biomass over the second half of the time series (2000-2011)
573 compared to the first half (1988-1999), despite some interannual variability in spatial
574 distribution. In 1988, when mean biomass was greatest, the biomass appeared evenly
575 distributed across the CAB and EAB, and across both inner and outer shelves. In 2007, when
576 mean biomass was lowest over the time series, biomass was particularly low over the WAB
577 and inner CAB compared to other areas on the Bank. In 2006, mean biomass was elevated
578 due to a localised patch of high biomass on the EAB, near 24°E . This ‘hotspot’ was present
579 for all the main taxa sampled apart from *Metridia lucens* (Figs. S3-S10).

580 Patterns of interannual variability in biomass over the time series differed between the
581 dominant copepod taxa (Fig. 11). The long-term pattern for *C. agulhensis* (Fig. 11a) was
582 similar to that for total copepod biomass, with very high levels in 1988 (on the CAB and
583 EAB) and a significant long-term decline thereafter ($r^2 = 0.48/0.52$ including/excluding 1988,
584 $p < 0.001$), with secondary peaks in 1996, 1998 and 2006. This declining trend, which was
585 evident for all three regions of the Agulhas Bank (Fig. S14a), was even more pronounced in
586 terms of the proportion of total copepod biomass comprised by *C. agulhensis* (Fig. S15, $r^2 =$
587 0.39 , $p = 0.001$).

588 *Calanoides natalis* biomass also was very high on the CAB and EAB in 1988 and much
589 lower in subsequent years (Fig. 11b), with secondary peaks in 1993, 1995 and 1998. There
590 was no significant long-term decline when the 1988 data were excluded, however.
591 *Centropages* spp. biomass showed strong (3 to 4-fold) interannual variability (Fig. 11c), with
592 greatest biomass usually located on the CAB, and lowest on the EAB. Biomass peaks were
593 observed in 1991, 1996, 2001, 2003 and 2006. *Metridia lucens* biomass was greatest on the
594 WAB (Fig. 11d), with strong peaks in 1996, 2000 and 2002, low on the CAB, and minimal
595 on the EAB. Biomass of the Oithonidae was more than three times above average on the
596 WAB and CAB in 1995 and 1996, and two times above average on the EAB (Fig. 11e), with
597 moderate interannual variability in other years. Biomass of the Oncaeidae was also very high
598 (over three times above average) on the WAB and CAB in 1995 (Fig. 11f), with moderate
599 interannual variability in other years. Biomass of *Pleuromamma* spp. was greatest on the
600 WAB, with similar lower levels on the CAB and EAB, and showed considerable interannual
601 variability in all areas (Fig. 11g). Biomass peaks were greatest in 1990, 1995, 1996 and 1998.

602 Mean biomass of the small calanoid copepods declined significantly over the time-series
603 ($r^2=0.33$, $p<0.01$), mainly due to a strong decline on the CAB ($r^2=0.40$, $p<0.001$). There were
604 marked fluctuations between 1991 and 1997, with biomass declining sharply in 1992, then

605 rising to peak levels in 1995 and 1996 before declining again in 1997 (Fig. 11h). There was a
606 secondary peak in biomass on the EAB during 2006. Despite the decline in small calanoid
607 biomass over the time series, the proportion of total copepod biomass comprised by this
608 group increased over time ($r^2 = 0.28$, $p < 0.01$; Fig. S15) and revealed an opposite trend to *C.*
609 *agulhensis*.

610 3.6 Interannual variability in biomass of *Calanus agulhensis* stages

611 Interannual variability in biomass of each stage of *C. agulhensis* over the time-series showed
612 some common patterns (Fig. 12). The very high biomass on the CAB and EAB during 1988
613 was evident for all copepodite stages, whereas the secondary peak in biomass during 1998
614 was particularly pronounced for the largest stages (females, males and C5s), was present but
615 less pronounced for C4s, and was not observed for the smaller stages (C3-C1) or nauplii. The
616 secondary peak in total *C. agulhensis* biomass during 2006 was observed to some extent in all
617 stages, but was most pronounced for the C1s and nauplii, while the youngest copepodite
618 stages (C1 to C3) also displayed secondary peaks in 1991 and 1993. Biomass of the large
619 calanoid nauplii fluctuated strongly over most of the time series. Biomass of all stages was,
620 with few exceptions, lowest on the WAB and greatest on either the CAB or EAB, with these
621 two areas showing similar fluctuations.

622

623 In addition to a significant decline in total biomass of *C. agulhensis*, there was also a
624 significant decline in the biomass of each copepodite stage, as well as of the nauplii (Fig. 12).
625 Declines in biomass were significant for all areas, and for all stages, except for nauplii on the
626 EAB, where high interannual variability in biomass was observed (Fig. 12j). In terms of total
627 *C. agulhensis* biomass, the proportion of female, C5 and C4 biomass declined significantly
628 over the time-series, while the proportion of C1 biomass, as well as that of C1-C3s combined,
629 increased significantly (Fig. S14).

630

631 3.7 Relationships with environmental variables

632 Despite the differing taxonomic patterns of variability over the time series, there were a few
633 cases of synchrony between taxa. A number of taxa displayed biomass peaks in 1995 and/or
634 1996 on the WAB and/or CAB (*Centropages* spp., *Metridia lucens*, Oithonidae,
635 *Pleuromamma* spp., small calanoids (Para- and Clausocalanidae). There was nothing
636 remarkable about 1995 in terms of the environmental variables measured in this study, but
637 1996 was the second-coldest year of the time-series, with the shallowest 17°C isotherm (Fig.
638 7a) and a strong cold ridge index (large area of cold water within the upper 30 m; Fig. 7b).
639 The very high biomass of *C. agulhensis* and *C. natalis* on the CAB and EAB in 1988 (and
640 relatively high biomass of small calanoids) also coincided with a strong cold ridge index in
641 both area and volume (Fig. 7b).

642 Peaks in biomass of *C. agulhensis* during 1988, 1989, 1996, 1998 and 2006 all coincided
643 with below average mean temperature (Fig. 7a) and high indices for the cold ridge area (Fig.
644 7b), as well as high cold ridge volume in 1988 and 1996. In contrast, there was no biomass

645 peak in 2009 when there was the largest cold ridge volume over the time series. The 1998
646 peak in biomass for the larger stages was also the year of maximum mean chl *a* concentration
647 throughout the water column (Fig. 7c; Fig. S13). Considering the time series overall,
648 however, it is difficult to see any consistent synchrony between the high indices for the cold
649 ridge or chl *a*, and the peaks in copepod biomass.

650 3.8 Synoptic view of the copepod dynamics

651 The nMDS gives an overall perspective of the data set and highlights the main differences
652 that clearly distinguish the three regions of the bank (Fig. 13). The copepod composition on
653 the WAB is clearly different to that on the EAB, with dominance by *M. lucens*,
654 *Pleurommama* spp. and Oncaeidae, whereas the EAB is more influenced by *C. natalis* and *C.*
655 *agulhensis*. The CAB samples are located between the EAB and WAB indicating an
656 intermediate copepod composition between the other two regions, with some larger overlap
657 for specific years (e.g., 1988 or 2000).

658 It is interesting to note that the *C. natalis* (all stages) and *C. agulhensis* (all stages) are well
659 differentiated in the ordination along the vertical axis, suggesting contrasting patterns of
660 relative abundance in some years. While *C. agulhensis* was consistently more abundant than
661 *C. natalis* on the Agulhas Bank over the time series, the ratio between the two species varied
662 considerably, from a minimum of 1.5 in 2011 (high relative abundance of *C. natalis* and low
663 relative abundance of *C. agulhensis*) to a maximum of 65.4 in 2001 (low relative abundance
664 of *C. natalis* and high relative abundance of *C. agulhensis*). Lastly, *Centropages* spp. is
665 located away from most of the other taxa suggesting that this species is most likely present in
666 all three areas during certain years, as was described above (mostly located on the inner bank
667 of the Agulhas Bank, Fig. S7).

668 Once again, the years 1988 and 1989 stand out for all three areas with dominance by *C.*
669 *agulhensis* and *C. natalis* (towards the left hand-side of the ordination). Some years such as
670 2005, 2007 and 2011 were, for all three regions, located together at the top of the ordination.
671 This may indicate some similarities that extended over the whole Agulhas Bank during those
672 years. These years had low biomass for most taxa (Fig. 11), but as the nMDS does not use
673 absolute values, it suggests that the relative contribution of each copepod species to total
674 biomass was similar during those years.

675 3.9 Relationship between copepods and pelagic fish biomass

676 Total pelagic fish biomass estimates from the November pelagic biomass surveys, comprising
677 combined data for anchovy, sardine and redeye for the entire Agulhas Bank (DAFF, 2018),
678 showed a generally contrasting trend to estimated copepod biomass over the time series (Fig.
679 14a). Following a period of relatively low biomass of ≤ 4 million tons prior to 1997, annual
680 spawner biomass increased rapidly to a peak of ca. 10 million tons in 2002, then declined
681 again to levels between 4-6 million tons from 2006 until 2011. Apart from the exceptionally
682 high peak in 1988, copepod biomass showed comparatively lower interannual variability over
683 the time series, with a general decline from 1989 to 2011, although there was a period of

684 greater variability between 1997 and 2000. Despite the interannual variability within both
685 data sets, there was a significant negative relationship ($r^2 = 0.25$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 24$) between
686 total copepod and total pelagic fish biomass over the Agulhas Bank during the study period
687 (Fig. 14b), with the period of high fish biomass over the second half of the time series
688 coinciding with relatively low copepod biomass. Mean copepod biomass was significantly
689 lower after 1996 (the year of the eastward shift for anchovy; Roy et al., 2007) compared to
690 before (Kruskal-Wallis test, $H = 7.69$, $p = 0.006$). There was also a significant (and slightly
691 stronger) negative relationship between total pelagic fish biomass and biomass of *C.*
692 *agulhensis* ($r^2 = 0.32$, $p < 0.01$, $n = 24$), and a weaker negative relationship with biomass of
693 small calanoids ($r^2 = 0.18$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 24$; Table 4).

694 When the various fish species were considered separately, we found significant negative
695 relationships between anchovy biomass and both total copepod and *C. agulhensis* biomass,
696 between redeye biomass and both total copepod and *C. agulhensis* biomass, and between
697 anchovy and redeye biomass combined and both total and *C. agulhensis* biomass (Table 4).
698 The strongest (negative) relationship over the time series was between redeye and *C.*
699 *agulhensis* ($r^2 = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$, $n = 24$). We also found significant negative relationships
700 between redeye biomass, and anchovy and redeye biomass combined, and biomass of the
701 small calanoids. None of the relationships between sardine biomass and any of the copepod
702 biomass categories tested above were significant (Table 4).

703

704 4. Discussion

705 4.1 Spatial patterns of copepods on the Agulhas Bank

706 4.1.1 Current and cruise-feeding herbivores

707 Copepod biomass on the Agulhas Bank during late spring was strongly dominated by the
708 large calanoid *C. agulhensis* and small calanoids of the Para- and Clausocalanidae, primarily
709 the smaller ‘myelinated current-feeding herbivores’ as defined by Benadetti et al. (2022).
710 Biomass of these taxa was most concentrated on the outer shelf between the 100 and 200 m
711 isobaths, extending over the central and eastern bank between 20 and 24°E. This distribution
712 was closely aligned with the region of greatest subsurface chl *a* biomass, downstream from
713 coastal and cold ridge-associated upwelling. Collectively these two groups accounted for over
714 50% of total copepod abundance and over 70% of total biomass. Although considered a
715 ‘large’ copepod for the Agulhas Bank, *C. agulhensis* is a relatively small *Calanus* species
716 compared to larger congeners found in high latitudes and polar regions with high turbulence
717 and strong seasonality, which group separately according to Benedetti et al. (2022).

718 While the distribution pattern of high biomass on the outer shelf of the CAB and EAB has
719 previously been observed for *C. agulhensis* (Peterson et al., 1992; Peterson and Hutchings,
720 1995; Huggett and Richardson, 2000), this is the first time it has been shown for the small
721 calanoids (Para- and Clausocalanidae). Previous studies have suggested the centre of *C.*
722 *agulhensis* biomass to be directly associated with the cold ridge, through a combination of

723 elevated chl *a* and retentive circulation (Peterson et al., 1992; Peterson and Hutchings, 1995).
724 This suggests that the cold ridge and coastal upwelling areas provide feeding conditions that
725 suit both the trophic group (omnivore-herbivore) and foraging behaviour (mainly current
726 feeding, with some cruise feeding within the Clausocalanidae) of these two groups of
727 calanoid copepods (Table 3). Considering the overlap in size between the smaller (younger
728 juvenile) stages of *C. agulhensis* and the larger (adult and older juvenile) small calanoids,
729 there is a likelihood of resource competition between these groups due to overlapping size-
730 based food preferences. However, larger copepods may also experience food availability
731 challenges. As feeding efficiency declines with increasing copepod size (Kiorboe 2011), and
732 larger copepods have greater daily total food requirements than smaller animals, larger
733 copepods are more frequently food limited compared to smaller copepods (Richardson and
734 Verheye, 1999). Both small and large current-feeding calanoids would therefore benefit from
735 elevated phytoplankton biomass associated with the cold ridge.

736 While the region of mean elevated chl *a* ($>0.9 \text{ mg m}^{-3}$) overlaps to some extent with the mean
737 signature of the cold ridge ($<17^\circ\text{C}$ at 30 m), the core region of greatest subsurface chl *a*
738 between $22\text{-}24^\circ\text{E}$ lies slightly offshore of the core ridge (i.e., cold water) area on the CAB,
739 seemingly sandwiched between the two branches of cool water. This high chl *a* feature then
740 seems to track the outer shelf in a south-westerly direction that follows the general flow
741 direction, as described by Roberts (2005), extending well beyond the direct influence of the
742 ridge towards the outer western bank. This pattern aligns closely with the mean pattern of
743 copepod biomass, suggesting that both phytoplankton and zooplankton biomass are
744 distributed, or dispersed, across the entire outer bank, following the mean flow patterns
745 driven by the Agulhas Current.

746 Whereas *C. agulhensis* stages were most closely associated with the above pattern, the small
747 calanoids were also abundant further east than *C. agulhensis*, where chl *a* was slightly lower,
748 which may favour their comparatively lower (total, as opposed to biomass-specific) food
749 requirements due to their smaller body size (although their relatively higher turnover rates
750 may act in opposition). Both *C. agulhensis* and the small calanoids would be prone to
751 advection by the Agulhas Current and general flow patterns, which could explain the
752 apparent accumulation of both taxa over the southern tip of the Bank. In addition to likely
753 losses offshore (offshelf), a portion of the population would eventually be lost from the
754 Agulhas Bank by downstream advection across the outer Bank, continuing up the west coast
755 of South Africa, where abundance of *C. agulhensis* is greatest beyond the 200 m isobath
756 (Huggett and Richardson, 2000; Huggett, 2003). However, cyclonic circulation around the
757 cold ridge, particularly along the western edge (Boyd & Shillington 1994), appears to aid
758 retention of some of the population on the CAB (see also Noyon et al., this issue), or at least
759 to delay advection downstream. Huggett (2003) showed that abundance of the larger stages of
760 *C. agulhensis* was significantly higher to the east in years (cruises) when the ridge was
761 present, compared to years when the ridge was absent.

762 The centres of gravity of *C. agulhensis* stages were located increasingly further offshore and
763 downstream from the cold ridge with increasing developmental stage, which is likely a

764 natural consequence of advection over time as individuals of each stage grow and moult to
765 the next stage. Increasing distance offshore, and thus increasing depth, with ontogenetic stage
766 would also facilitate the greater extent of DVM with increasing body size for *C. agulhensis*.
767 Larger copepods typically feed in the surface or subsurface chl *a* maximum at night, when the
768 risk from visual predators is reduced, then descend to the relatively safety of deeper waters
769 during the day where low light levels provide further protection from predators (Haney, 1988;
770 Hays, 2003). This has previously been demonstrated for *C. agulhensis* in a water column
771 depth of 100 m on the Agulhas Bank, with most copepodite stages (C2 to adults) descending
772 to 80-100 m during the day after feeding in food-rich conditions near the surface at night
773 (Huggett and Richardson, 2000; Huggett, 2003). Increasing body size imparts an increasing
774 risk of visibility to predators such as pelagic fish, thus larger species and developmental
775 stages tend to exhibit pronounced DVM, whereas smaller species generally do not perform
776 DVM or else perform very limited DVM (10s of metres as opposed to 100s of metres,
777 Benedetti et al., 2016), tending to remain at the surface for longer periods (Hays et al., 2001).
778 This may necessitate a trade-off between food availability and predator avoidance, with
779 individuals sometimes delaying their dusk descent, or starting their dawn ascent earlier, to
780 maximise time feeding near the surface when food abundance is low, despite the heightened
781 risk of predation (Hays et al., 1995; Huggett and Richardson, 2000).

782 Interestingly, *C. agulhensis* adult males were less widely dispersed and more closely located
783 to the secondary centre of biomass of all stages south of Plettenberg Bay, and north of the
784 Agulhas Bight, suggesting an additional mechanism for retention in this area. Lutjeharms et
785 al. (1989) found shear edge cyclonic eddies to be prevalent within the Agulhas Bank shelf
786 bight, between the shelf edge and inner border of the Agulhas Current. A subsequent
787 modelling study suggested that shear edge eddies remain trapped in the bight, resulting in a
788 near stationary, or 'resident' shear eddy ca. 50-100 km in diameter (Lutjeharms et al. 2003).
789 *Calanus* males are known to have shorter lifespans than those of females (Hatlebakk et al.,
790 2019), although this has not been assessed locally for *C. agulhensis*, but is supported by the
791 much lower abundance of males compared to females.

792 Another large current-feeding herbivore, the upwelling-associated species *Calanoides natalis*,
793 was associated with the outer edge of the Agulhas Bank, although at far lower biomass levels
794 than those of the similarly sized *C. agulhensis*, and also much lower compared to the
795 population biomass levels typically associated with the Benguela upwelling ecosystem where
796 it is one of the key species. *C. natalis* occurs in a number of African upwelling systems,
797 including the Benguela (Verheye et al., 1991; Timonin et al., 1992; Bode et al., 2014),
798 equatorial West Africa (Binet and Suisse de Sainte Claire, 1975; Peterson, 1998; Höring et
799 al., 2017) and the Somali and western Arabian Sea upwelling systems (Smith, 1982;
800 Piontovski et al., 2015). It has been shown to diapause in deep water in areas of strong
801 seasonal disparity in food abundance, such as the Arabian Sea (Smith and Madhupratap
802 2005). *C. natalis* has also been collected in deep water off Madagascar (De Decker and
803 Mombeck, 1964), and is associated with upwelling off Durban (Carter 1977), suggesting a
804 possible circum-African distribution at depth (Bradford-Grieve et al., 2017). During the
805 November surveys, biomass of this species was low on the Agulhas Bank, but was greatest

806 along the eastern shelf-edge, particularly in the Agulhas Bight area. This is in agreement with
807 earlier work by Huggett (2003), who found low abundances of both immature and adult
808 stages along much of the shelf-edge during a cruise in January 1992, again most likely linked
809 to the shelf-edge upwelling, and potentially to sporadic shear edge cyclonic eddies in the
810 Agulhas Bight region (Lutjeharms et al., 1989; Lutjeharms et al., 2003), which would both
811 stimulate production through core upwelling and enhance retention of entrained plankton on
812 the outer bank. Nutrient enrichment from current-driven upwelling along the shelf-edge,
813 however, is of a much lower magnitude compared to that from wind-driven coastal upwelling
814 that typifies the Benguela upwelling system, and enhanced production along the shelf-edge
815 tends to occur deeper in the water column. Spatial separation between *C. natalis* and the core
816 *C. agulhensis* community suggests competition for food between these similarly sized species
817 is unlikely, but offshore advection by the fast-flowing Agulhas Current is likely to inhibit the
818 establishment of a permanent community here.

819 4.1.2 Current or cruise-feeding detritivores

820 *Metridia lucens* and the Oncaeidae, which fall in this category, both displayed biomass
821 patterns most closely associated with the western sector of the Agulhas Bank, although were
822 largely absent from the cooler inshore region of the WAB. While *M. lucens* was largely
823 restricted to the relatively chl-rich outer shelf of the WAB, peak oncaeid biomass overlapped
824 broadly with the extensive western region characterised by a deep upper mixed layer,
825 extending eastwards to around 21°E, suggesting more differences than similarities in niche
826 preference between these groups.

827 *Metridia* spp. are usually considered to be omnivorous. Gut content and fatty acid analysis
828 studies indicate their diets may include diatoms, particularly during bloom conditions, but
829 also dinoflagellates, tintinnids, radiolarians and copepod nauplii in addition to detritus
830 (Hattori 1989; Osgood and Frost 1994; Liu and Hopcroft 2006; Teuber et al. 2014; Fields
831 2015). They are known strong migrators, generally undertaking extensive DVM from
832 mesopelagic daytime depths to shallower depths at night in order to benefit from a richer
833 food supply in epipelagic layers (Hays et al. 2001; Liu and Hopcroft 2006; Teuber et al.
834 2014; Fields 2015). Highest biomass of *M. lucens* on the WAB coincided with regions of
835 elevated chl *a*, suggesting that phytoplankton (or the associated microplankton community)
836 maybe an important food resource for this species. Gut content analysis from the Benguela
837 upwelling region has yielded both phytoplankton and zooplankton, primarily copepod,
838 remains (Shannon and Pillar, 1986).

839 *M. lucens* is one of several dominant copepod species in both the southern and northern
840 Benguela upwelling ecosystems (Verheye et al., 1992; Bode et al., 2014). In the southern
841 Benguela it comprises 30% of total copepod biomass on average and is most concentrated
842 over the continental shelf, downstream from the main upwelling cells, where it is more
843 common in deep (>100 m) than shallow water (Gibbons, 1993). Its concentration on the outer
844 WAB, with low biomass elsewhere on the Bank, suggests this may be an extension of the
845 west coast (Benguela) population. This might seem counter-intuitive, given the predominant

846 northwestward flow from the WAB towards the South African west coast (Shelton &
847 Hutchings 1982; Boyd and Nelson, 1998). However, Boyd and Nelson (1998) also observed
848 marked southward flow in this region during summer, providing a possible mechanism for
849 west coast fauna such as *M. lucens* to be advected towards the Agulhas Bank. Jackson et al.
850 (2012) measured strong (0.5 m s^{-1}) southeastward flow along the 500 m isobath of the WAB
851 due to the presence of a cyclonic eddy, providing an additional route from the west coast to
852 the Agulhas Bank, although such an eddy could also remove biota from the shelf. These
853 eddies are thought to form at irregular intervals when the Agulhas Current detaches from the
854 southern tip of the Agulhas Bank (Penven et al., 2001). Thus, although flow on the WAB is
855 generally equatorward, at times it may be poleward, particularly along the southern part of
856 the shelf edge (Lutjeharms et al., 2007).

857 The family Oncaeidae is a diverse and taxonomically complex group of small cyclopoids.
858 They are difficult to identify, owing to their small size, high species diversity (>100 species
859 known to date; Sun et al., 2022), and the lack of fundamental taxonomic knowledge (Böttger-
860 Schnack et al., 2004). Their diet includes a wide spectrum of prey, ranging from
861 phytoplankton cells and flagellates to crustacean plankton and appendicularians. Their
862 substrate-feeding modus enables them to utilize colonial phytoplankton cells (*Phaeocystis*
863 spp.) and marine snow aggregates in surface waters, and they are thought to use
864 appendicularian houses (and potentially other gelatinous taxa such as Thaliacea and
865 Siphonophora) as both habitat and food source (Böttger-Schnack et al., 1989; Ohtsuka et al.,
866 1993; Böttger-Schnack et al., 2004; Turner, 2004). Long female longevity and a lifetime
867 reproductive output similar to that of co-occurring small calanoids (Para- and
868 Clausocalanidae), which reproduce at higher daily rates, but over shorter lifetimes, likely
869 contribute to their high abundance, despite high mortality rates from predation (Turner,
870 2004).

871 Greatest oncaeid biomass was closely associated with the western and central sectors of the
872 Agulhas Bank, beyond the 100 m isobath, characterised by a markedly deeper mixed layer
873 compared to the eastern sector. Lying offshore and downstream from the cooler coastal and
874 cold ridge upwelling areas respectively, this region favours dense populations of thaliaceans
875 (salps and doliolids, typically *Thalia democratica* and *Doliolum denticulatum*) which “can
876 occur in incredible numbers over the central and southern parts of the Bank, their
877 uninterrupted swarms extending over thousands of square miles” (De Decker, 1973, p. 196).
878 Gibbons (1997) noted that thaliaceans are most abundant and attain greatest areal coverage
879 during spring and summer, when the Agulhas Bank becomes strongly stratified (Probyn et al.,
880 1994). Such conditions thus seem conducive to both oncaeids and thaliaceans and may point
881 to a close association between the two, as suggested by Böttger-Schnack et al. (1989).

882 4.1.3 Current or ambush-feeding omnivores

883 This category includes the small to medium-sized *Centropages* spp. (amyelinated current-
884 ambush-feeding omnivores/herbivores) and the very small Oithoinidae (amyelinated ambush-
885 feeding omnivores) which displayed biomass patterns closely aligned with the inner to mid-
886 shelf region of the western and central Agulhas Bank, away from the main influence of the

887 Agulhas Current. This region is characterised by warmer, more stable conditions with
888 variable chl a concentration, being relatively poor on the inner CAB but elevated on the mid-
889 shelf region of the CAB and the outer WAB shelf. The third component of this category is
890 comprised by the much larger *Pleuromamma* spp., current-feeding omnivores which were
891 tightly clustered beyond the WAB shelf-edge.

892 Several *Centropages* species occur on the Agulhas Bank, including *C. brachiatus*, which is
893 abundant in the cool, chlorophyll-rich inshore waters of the Benguela upwelling system off
894 the west coasts of South Africa and Namibia (De Decker, 1984; Shannon and Pillar, 1986).
895 *C. brachiatus* also occurs on the Agulhas Bank but appears to be less abundant and
896 widespread compared to *C. chierchiae* which, like *C. agulhensis*, has its centre of dispersal
897 on the Agulhas Bank (De Decker, 1984). *C. furcatus* is also common on the bank but is more
898 closely associated with the Agulhas Current. Biomass of the Centropagidae overall was
899 comparatively low on the Agulhas Bank compared to the west coast of South Africa,
900 comprising 4% of total copepod biomass overall compared to 7% on the west coast (J.
901 Huggett, unpublished data). Highest biomass on the bank coincided with cooler, more
902 productive (relatively chlorophyll-rich) regions associated with wind-driven upwelling on the
903 inner WAB, considered a natural extension of the west coast upwelling system (Probyn et al.
904 1994), and the cold ridge on the CAB. Given the somewhat bimodal aspect to the distribution
905 of *Centropages* spp, biomass on the Agulhas Bank, it seems feasible that the biomass hotspot
906 on the inner WAB may be an extension of the west coast (southern Benguela) *C. brachiatus*
907 community, while the region of elevated biomass on the CAB aligned with the cold ridge is
908 likely to be dominated by *C. chierchiae*, but this remains a topic for further investigation.

909 The Oithonidae are small (mostly <1 mm), omnivorous ambush predators, and along with the
910 Oncaidae are the most abundant metazoans in the ocean (Paffenhöfer, 1993; Gallienne and
911 Robins, 2001; Turner, 2004). They are ubiquitous, occurring in all parts of the ocean from
912 polar to tropical regions, from estuaries to coastal and offshore waters, and in both epipelagic
913 and mesopelagic environments (Paffenhöfer, 1993; Castellani et al., 2015). However, they
914 have historically been under sampled due to the widespread use of nets with mesh sizes ≥ 200
915 μm . Although widespread, they attain greatest abundances in coastal and shelf waters, where
916 they are important prey items for larval fish and other zooplanktivorous consumers (Turner,
917 2004). Some species have been shown to prey selectively on motile prey such as ciliates and
918 dinoflagellates (Lonsdale et al., 2000; Castellani et al., 2005; Nishibe et al., 2010; Zamora-
919 Terol et al., 2014), providing an important link between the microbial food web and higher
920 trophic levels (Wang et al., 2017; Cornwall et al., 2020). Some are primary consumers of
921 phytoplankton (Porri et al., 2007), while others are speculated to be coprophagous, feeding on
922 faecal pellets and helping to remove faecal material from the euphotic zone, with the ability
923 to use this ubiquitous food source efficiently contributing to the widespread occurrence of
924 this genus (González and Smetacek, 1994). Furthermore, since cyclopoid taxa such as the
925 Oithonidae show generally less specialization than calanoids, and have comparatively low
926 daily rations, they are able to survive over an extended range of environmental conditions
927 (Paffenhöfer, 1993).

928 Biomass of Oithonidae on the Agulhas Bank was low (<1% of total copepod biomass)
929 compared to the west coast, where biomass commonly exceeds 1 g C m⁻² in the inshore
930 upwelling zone north of Cape Columbine and comprised 17% of total copepod biomass
931 (during biannual cruises from 1988-2003; J. Huggett, unpublished data). *Oithona similis* is
932 the dominant species off the west coast, comprising 90% of abundance for the genus, and up
933 to 60% of total copepod abundance (Pillar, 1984; Gibbons, 1993). With biomass levels
934 particularly low over the Agulhas Current-influenced outer shelf, this suggests that the
935 comparatively warm Agulhas Bank is a suboptimal environment for this group compared to
936 the cooler southern Benguela upwelling region.

937 *Pleuromamma* spp. tend to have even deeper daytime distributions than *Metridia* spp., with
938 their large size and strong swimming ability assisting to mitigate their higher predation risk
939 due to their greater visibility. Other studies have shown their abundance to peak between
940 400-1000 m during the day, and between 70-100 m at night (Fields, 2015). Some species are
941 particularly tolerant of low oxygen conditions, such as *P. indica* and *P. abdominalis*, which
942 can survive in water columns with oxygen concentrations as low as 0.1 and 0.2 ml L⁻¹
943 respectively (Saraswathy and Krishnaiyer, 1986), although the higher levels of oxygenation
944 in Agulhas Bank bottom water compared to the Benguela upwelling system (Roberts 2005)
945 suggest that this is unlikely to be of consideration. *Pleuromamma* spp. were not abundant on
946 the Agulhas Bank, comprising just 2% of total copepod biomass. Their preference for deeper
947 water explains the area of greatest biomass being located beyond the shelf edge of the WAB,
948 with very low biomass elsewhere over the outer shelf region. De Decker (1973) found four
949 species “avoiding the Bank but commonly found on the edge of the shelf and beyond”,
950 namely *P. abdominalis*, *P. borealis*, *P. piskei*, and *P. xiphias*.

951 4.2 Ecosystem variability and implications for bottom-up versus top-down control of 952 copepods on the Agulhas Bank

953 The significant decline observed for total copepod biomass on the Agulhas Bank over the 24-
954 year time series was echoed in each developmental stage of *C. agulhensis*, from the nauplii
955 through to the adults, as well as in the small calanoids (Para- and Clausocalanidae) but was
956 not apparent for any of the other major copepod taxa. The abundance and specific structure
957 (size and species composition) of zooplankton communities is widely considered to be
958 controlled from both the ‘top down’ and the ‘bottom up’ – from the top by predation, due to
959 species-specific vulnerability to predators such as planktivorous fish, and from the bottom by
960 food levels, due to species-specific efficiency in food utilisation (Gliwicz, 2002). Long-term
961 changes in zooplankton may thus be mediated by environmental factors influencing food
962 availability, or predation pressure, or a combination of the two, although they can be difficult
963 to disentangle (Verheye et al., 1998; Verheye, 2000). Top-down forcing influences
964 zooplankton biomass, individual body size and population density, whereas bottom-up forces
965 influence feeding, individual growth rates and reproduction (Gliwicz, 2002).

966 Bottom-up changes to food quantity and quality for zooplankton may ensue from
967 environmental changes mediated by climate forcing, such as ocean warming, upwelling
968 intensity, or shifts in circulation patterns leading to altered nutrient supply or advective

969 losses. Climate models (e.g., Yang et al., 2016) suggest that western boundary currents, such
970 as the Agulhas Current, will intensify and shift poleward due to intensifying winds caused by
971 climate change. In contrast to this, projections for the next 100 years from a coupled
972 physical-biogeochemical model (NEMO-MEDUSA) suggest an equatorial shift of the
973 Agulhas Current, resulting in increased current velocity on the Agulhas Bank (Asdar et al.,
974 this issue). This is more in agreement with Beal and Elipot (2016), who showed that the
975 Agulhas Current has not intensified since the early 1990s but has instead broadened due to
976 increased eddy activity. They suggest the likely consequence is a more porous divide between
977 continental shelves and the open ocean, leading to greater mixing and cross-frontal exchange
978 of nutrients. Such changes could enhance current-induced upwelling (and thus nutrient input)
979 over the shelf, although Asdar et al. (this issue) suggest that future increases in nutrient
980 concentrations are unlikely to impact primary production. This may be due to the nutrients
981 being trapped in the bottom waters and the strong stratification already inherent on the
982 Agulhas Bank (Probyn et al., 1994). On the other hand, increased eddy activity and/or
983 increased current velocity over the shelf could also lead to increased advective losses of biota
984 from the shelf towards the open ocean (Asdar et al., this issue; Jacobs et al., this issue).
985 Further studies will be required to shed further light on the likelihood and frequency of these
986 scenarios.

987 Studies using satellite remote sensing data for temperature (i.e., reflecting the surface skin of
988 the ocean) have shown a long-term warming trend for the Agulhas Current system over the
989 past 3-4 decades (1982-2010, Blamey et al., 2015; 1982-2019, Sweijd and Smit, 2020),
990 particularly along the Agulhas Bank shelf edge. Warming in this region was described as
991 'superfast' compared to 'moderate' over the interior of the Agulhas Bank (Sweijd and Smit,
992 2020). Consensus is that ocean warming will result in stronger stratification, reduced vertical
993 nutrient fluxes, and hence reduced chl *a* (e.g., Capotondi et al., 2012, Yamaguchi & Suga,
994 2019). In response, the structure of phytoplankton communities is expected to shift from
995 large-species dominance (microplankton, >20 μm) to smaller nanophytoplankton and
996 picophytoplankton as warming occurs. These combined effects would likely lead to reduced
997 food availability for herbivorous copepods in general, and poorer food quality for larger
998 copepods that prefer larger-celled phytoplankton (Richardson and Verheye, 1998). Lamont et
999 al. (2019) showed, based on modelled remote sensed data (Brewin et al. 2010), that
1000 microphytoplankton constituted ca. 40-50% of the total chl *a* biomass on the Agulhas Bank,
1001 and revealed weak decreases during all seasons except summer over a 15-year period. This
1002 could suggest a decrease in food quality for grazers as explained above with possible
1003 repercussions for the rest of the food web. However, it is important to note that the decreases
1004 observed are small, are from modelled surface data only, and contradict the long-term trend
1005 from the NEMO-MEDUSA model (Asdar et al., this issue). Too little is yet understood in
1006 terms of the potential impact of stratification on phytoplankton dynamics for the Agulhas
1007 Bank (see Poulton et al., this issue), with results to date highlighting the complexity of this
1008 environment.

1009 In contrast to the satellite data, in situ temperature data collected over the Agulhas Bank
1010 during the November surveys from this study did not indicate any trends, whether from near

1011 the surface or in deeper (30 m) water, whereas in situ chl *a* showed a significant, but weak
1012 (1.5% yr⁻¹), increase over the series. Lamont et al. (2019) observed a small but significant
1013 long-term increase in Chl *a* during summer (Dec-Feb), a significant decrease in autumn (Mar-
1014 May), and no obvious trends during winter (Jun-Aug) or spring (Sep-Nov) from 2002-2018.
1015 Most recently, Mazwane et al. (this issue) found a slight but significant decline in satellite-
1016 derived rates of Net Primary Production (NPP) rates on the Agulhas Bank over a 21-year
1017 period (1998-2018), which overlaps with the second half of our study. Most of the decline
1018 was on the central bank between 100 m and 200 m isobaths, which coincides with the
1019 copepod biomass maximum found in our study. Overall, these ambiguous patterns do not
1020 suggest any synergistic or marked changes in food availability for zooplankton during the 24-
1021 year study. However, this may not be completely unexpected, as approximately 32–36 years
1022 of observations are considered necessary to be able to distinguish long-term climate-driven
1023 trends from interannual to decadal variations in chl *a* (Hensen et al., 2010; Lamont et al.,
1024 2019), and hence potential long-term changes in food availability for zooplankton.

1025 In contrast to bottom-up forcing of zooplankton variability, top-down forcing through
1026 predation by planktivorous fish or invertebrate predators such as squid or carnivorous
1027 gelatinous zooplankton tends to have shorter-term and more discernible impacts, and
1028 generally overrides the more gradual influence of bottom-up processes (Gliwicz, 2002). The
1029 Agulhas Bank is a traditional spawning ground for many small pelagic fish such as anchovy,
1030 sardine, redeye round herring and horse mackerel that feed on zooplankton (Hutchings et al.,
1031 2002). Copepods are thought to provide a nutritious food source for many of these fish,
1032 invertebrate predators and their respective larvae, including paralarvae of chokka squid that
1033 spawn on the EAB (Augustyn et al., 1994; Roberts, 2005), as has been observed in other
1034 systems (e.g., García-Mayoral et al., 2022).

1035 There have been marked changes in both the abundance and distribution of small pelagic fish
1036 on the Agulhas Bank over the past few decades (Roy et al., 2007; Blamey et al., 2015). In the
1037 late 1980s and early to mid-1990s, adult anchovy were concentrated on the WAB, from
1038 where their eggs and larvae were transported to the west coast nursery area by the Benguela
1039 jet current (Shelton and Hutchings, 1990; Huggett et al., 1998). Since 1996, however, the
1040 bulk of anchovy spawners have been located east of Cape Agulhas, on the CAB and EAB
1041 (van der Lingen et al., 2006; van der Lingen and Hampton, 2018). A more gradual, but
1042 similar, change was observed in sardine, with an increasing proportion of biomass observed
1043 east of Cape Agulhas since 1999 (Coetzee et al., 2008b). The eastward shift in sardine
1044 distribution has had significant ramifications for the ecosystem in general, and in particular
1045 for seabirds such as Cape gannets and African penguins that depend on sardine for prey
1046 (Blamey et al., 2015). Despite this sudden shift, the copepods seem to have decreased steadily
1047 during spring over the time series, with no dramatic shift in biomass observed around 1996,
1048 or in response to peak fish biomass in 2002. Nevertheless, the significant negative
1049 relationship between total copepod biomass and total pelagic fish biomass suggests an
1050 important top-down influence from predation pressure by zooplanktivorous fish on the
1051 Agulhas Bank copepod community, with spatial mismatch between copepods and fish
1052 possibly contributing to the variance between the two data sets. The influence of

1053 environmental forcing cannot be ruled out, however, and may be a contributing factor to the
1054 long-term reduction in copepod biomass on the Agulhas Bank.

1055 *4.3 Ecosystem implications and conclusions*

1056 The proximal impact of increased predation on copepods, due to the increased biomass of
1057 planktivorous fish on the CAB and EAB in the latter part of the time series, is likely an
1058 important contributing factor in the significant decline observed in total copepod biomass, as
1059 well as the gradual shift to a greater proportion of smaller copepods, due to size-selective
1060 predation by anchovy in particular (van der Lingen et al., 2009). This reduced biomass is
1061 likely to persist if the fish biomass remains concentrated east of Cape Agulhas but may also
1062 rebound in the short-term if fish biomass declines. In situ measurements of temperature and
1063 chl *a* during the surveys have not yielded any clear evidence of an altered food environment
1064 over the time series, which is perhaps not surprising given that the data come from temporally
1065 brief ‘snapshots’ of the environmental conditions, and that longer time series than ours are
1066 generally required for climatic influences to be discernible. In addition, the Agulhas Bank is a
1067 highly spatially and temporally variable environment due to the presence of one of the
1068 strongest boundary currents in the world, which considerably influences the shelf biota.

1069 An emerging shift towards smaller zooplankton, as observed during this study, will tend to
1070 favour sardine over anchovy, since sardine feed on smaller zooplankton prey compared to
1071 anchovy (van der Lingen et al., 2009). However, the decline in larger zooplankton contributes
1072 to a decline in total zooplankton biomass over time, and hence total food availability for all
1073 zooplanktivorous species on the Agulhas Bank, most notably the pelagic fish. A similar
1074 outcome is expected to accompany increased warming of the ecosystem in the long term, as
1075 copepods have been shown to follow Bergmann’s rule, whereby body size decreases with
1076 increasing temperature (Gardner et al., 2011; Campbell et al., 2021). The long-term
1077 ecosystem effects of a warming ocean due to climate change will result in a plankton
1078 assemblage dominated by smaller copepods, yielding lower copepod biomass overall, and
1079 consequently potentially lower fisheries production as well as carbon sequestration
1080 (Campbell et al., 2021).

1081

1082 **Acknowledgements**

1083 This publication was supported by the SOLSTICE-WIO UKGCRF grant NE/P021050/1 and
1084 the ZOOLOGIC networking grant from Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science.
1085 Margaux Noyon received financial support from the Global Challenges Research Fund
1086 (GCRF), UK, in the framework of the SOLSTICE-WIO project (NE/P021050/1) as well as
1087 from the UK-SA bilateral chair Ocean Science and marine food security funded by the British
1088 Council Newton Fund grant SARCI 1503261 16102/ NRF 98399. Jacob Carstensen was
1089 supported by the GES4SEAS project, funded by the European Union under the Horizon
1090 Europe program (grant agreement no. 101059877), www.ges4seas.eu. We thank Catherine

1091 Boucher for her assistance with the copepod drawings. Comments and suggestions from two
1092 anonymous reviewers helped us to improve the text significantly.

1093

1094 **Appendix A. Supplementary data**

1095 Supplementary data to this article can be found online at ...

1096

1097 **References**

1098 Asdar, M., Jacobs, Z., Popova, E., Noyon, M., Sauer, W.H.H., Roberts, M. This issue.
1099 Projected climate change impacts on the ecosystems of the Agulhas Bank, South
1100 Africa. Deep sea Res. Part II top. Stud. Oceanogr.

1101 Augustyn, C.J., Lipinski, M.R., Sauer, W.H.H., Roberts, M.J., Mitchell-Innes, B.A., 1994.
1102 Chokka squid on the Agulhas Bank: life history and ecology. S. Afr. J. Sci. 90, 143-
1103 154.

1104 Beal, L.M., Elipot, S. 2016. Broadening not strengthening of the Agulhas Current since the
1105 early 1990s. Nature 540, 570-577. doi:10.1038/nature19853

1106 Becker, E.C., Mazzocchi, M.G., de Macedo-Soares, L.C.P., 2021. Latitudinal gradient of
1107 copepod functional diversity in the South Atlantic Ocean. Prog. Oceanogr. 199,
1108 102710.

1109 Benedetti, F., 2015. Mediterranean copepods' functional traits. PANGAEA.
1110 <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.854331>

1111 Benedetti, F., Gasparini, S., Ayata, S.-D., 2016. Identifying copepod functional groups from
1112 species functional traits. J. Plankton Res. 38, 159-166.
1113 <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbv096>

1114 Benedetti, F., Vogt, M., Righetti, D., Guilhaumon, F., Ayata, S.-D., 2018. Do functional
1115 groups of planktonic copepods differ in their ecological niches?
1116 J. Biogeogr. 45, 604-616. DOI: 10.1111/jbi.13166

1117 Benedetti, F., Wydler, J., Vogt, M., 2022. Copepod functional traits and groups show
1118 divergent biogeographies in the global ocean. J. Biogeogr.,
1119 <https://doi.org/10.1111/jbi.14512>

1120 Binet, D., Suisse de Sainte Claire, E., 1975. Le copéptide planctonique *Calanoides carinatus*
1121 répartition et cycle biologique au large de la Cote d'Ivoire. Cah. O.R.S.T.O.M., sér.
1122 Océanogr., 13, 15-30.

1123 Blamey, L.K., Shannon, L.J., Bolton, J.L., Crawford, R.J.M., Dufois, F., Evers-King, H.,
1124 Griffiths, C.L. et al., 2015. Ecosystem change in the southern Benguela and the

- 1125 underlying processes. *J. Mar. Syst.* 144, 9–29.
 1126 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2014.11.006>
- 1127 Bode, M., Kreiner, A., van der Plas, A.K., Louw, D.C., Horaeb, R., Auel, H., Hagen, W.,
 1128 2014. Spatio-Temporal Variability of Copepod Abundance along the 20°S Monitoring
 1129 Transect in the Northern Benguela Upwelling System from 2005 to 2011. *PLoS ONE*
 1130 9(5): e97738. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0097738
- 1131 Böttger-Schnack, R., Schnack, D., Weikert, H., 1989. Biological observations on small
 1132 cyclopoid copepods in the Red Sea. *J. Plankton. Res.* 1, 1089-1101.
- 1133 Böttger-Schnack, R., Lenz, J., Weikert, H., 2004. Are taxonomic details of relevance to
 1134 ecologists? An example from oncaeid microcopepods of the Red Sea. *Mar. Biol.* 114,
 1135 1127-1140.
- 1136 Boyd, A.J., Nelson, G., 1998. Variability of the Benguela Current off the Cape Peninsula,
 1137 South Africa. *S. Afr. J. Sci.* 19, 27-39. <https://doi.org/10.2989/025776198784126665>
- 1138 Boyd, A.J., Shillington, F.A., 1994. Physical forcing and circulation patterns on the Agulhas
 1139 Bank. *S. Afr. J. Sci.* 90, 114-122.
- 1140 Bradford-Grieve, J.M., Blanco-Bercial, L., Prusova, I., 2017. *Calanoides natalis* Brady, 1914
 1141 (Copepoda: Calanoida: Calanidae): identity and distribution in relation to coastal
 1142 oceanography of the eastern Atlantic and western Indian Oceans. *J. Nat. Hist.* 51, 807-
 1143 836. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2017.1296198>
- 1144 Brewin, R.J.W., Sathyendranath, S., Hirata, T., Lavender, S., Barciela, R.M., Hardman-
 1145 Mountford, N.J., 2010. A three-component model of phytoplankton size class for the
 1146 Atlantic Ocean. *Ecol. Modell.* 168, 437–450. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2015.07.004>
- 1147 Brun, P., Payne, M.R., Kiørboe, T., 2017. A trait database for marine copepods. *Earth System*
 1148 *Science Data* 9, 99-113. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-9-99-2017>
- 1149 Brun, P., Payne, M.R., Kiørboe, T., 2016. A trait database for marine copepods. *PANGAEA*,
 1150 <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.862968>
- 1151 Campbell, M.D., Schoeman, D.S., Venables, W., Abu-Alhaija, R., Batten, S.D., Chiba, S.,
 1152 Coman, F., Davies, C.H., Edwards, M., Eriksen, R., Everett, J.D., Fukai, Y., Fukuchi,
 1153 M., Garrote, O.E., Hosie, G., Huggett, J., Johns, D.G., Kitchener, J.A., Koubbi, P.,
 1154 McEnnulty, F.R., Muxagata, E., Ostle, C., Robinson, K.V., Slotwinski, A., Swadling,
 1155 K.M., Takahashi, K.T., Tonks, M., Uribe-Palomino, J., Verheye, H.M., Wilson, W.,
 1156 Worship, M., Yamaguchi, A., Zhang, W., Richardson, A.J., 2021. Testing Bergmann’s
 1157 Rule in marine copepods. *Ecography*, 44, 1283-1295, 2021. [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.05545)
 1158 [10.1111/ecog.05545](https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.05545)

- 1159 Capotondi, A., Alexander, M.A., Bond, N.A., Curchitser, E.N., Scott, J.D., 2012. Enhanced
1160 upper ocean stratification with climate change in the CMIP3 models. *J. Geophys. Res.*
1161 *Oceans*, 117(4). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JC007409>
- 1162 Carter, R.A. 1977. The distribution of calanoid copepoda in the Agulhas Current system off
1163 Natal, South Africa. M.Sc. thesis, University of Natal: 165 pp.
- 1164 Castellani, C., Irigoien, X., Harris, R.P., Lampitt, R.S., 2005. Feeding and egg production of
1165 *Oithona similis* in the North Atlantic. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 288, 173-182.
- 1166 Castellani, C., Licandro, P., Fileman, E., di Capua, I., Mazzocchi, M.G., 2015. *Oithona*
1167 *similis* likes it cool: evidence from two long-term time series. *J. Plankton. Res.* 38(3),
1168 703–717, <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbv104>
- 1169 Chang, N., 2008. Numerical ocean model study of the Agulhas Bank and the Cool Ridge.
1170 PhD Thesis, University of Cape Town, South Africa.
- 1171 Cleve. P.T., 1904. Plankton of the South African seas. 1. Copepoda. *Marine Investigations in*
1172 *South Africa* 3, 177-210.
- 1173 Coetzee, J.C., Merkle, D., de Moor, C.L., Twatwa, N.M., Barange, M., Butterworth, D.S.,
1174 2008a. Refined estimates of South African pelagic fish biomass from hydro-acoustic
1175 surveys: quantifying the effects of target strength, signal attenuation and receiver
1176 saturation. *Afr. J. Mar. Sci.* 30(2), 205–217.
- 1177 Coetzee, J.C., van der Lingen, C.D., Hutchings, L., Fairweather, T.P., 2008b. Has the fishery
1178 contributed to a major shift in the distribution of South African sardine? *ICES Mar. Sci.*
1179 *Symp.* 65, 1676–1688. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsn184>
- 1180 Cornwell, L.E., Fileman, E.S., Bruun, J.T., Hirst, A.G., Tarran, G.A., Findlay, H.S., Lewis,
1181 C., Smyth, T.J., McEvoy, A.J., Atkinson, A., 2020. Resilience of the copepod *Oithona*
1182 *similis* to climatic variability: egg production, mortality, and vertical habitat
1183 partitioning. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 29. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmars.2020.00029>.
- 1184 Crawford, R.J.M., Randall, R.M., Cook, T.R., Ryan, P.G., Dyer, B.M., Fox, R., Geldenhuys,
1185 D., Huisamen, J., McGeorge, J., Smith, M.K., Upfold, L., Visagie, J., Waller, L.J.,
1186 Whittington, P.A., Wilke, C.G., Makhado, A.B., 2016. Cape cormorants decrease,
1187 move east and adapt foraging strategies following eastward displacement of their main
1188 prey. *Afr. J. Mar. Sci.* 38(3), 373-383, <https://doi.org/10.2989/1814232X.2016.1202861>
- 1189 Crawford, R.J.M., Sabarros, P.S., Fairweather, T., Underhill, L.G., Wolfaardt, A.C., 2008.
1190 Implications for seabirds off South Africa of a long-term change in the distribution of
1191 sardine. *Afr. J. Mar. Sci.* 30, 177–184.
- 1192 Cressie, N.A.C., 1993. *Statistics for Spatial Data*, Rev. ed. Wiley, New York. MR1239641
- 1193 DAFF, 2018. Results of the 2018 pelagic biomass survey. Branch: Fisheries Management,
1194 Scientific Working Group – Small Pelagics. FISHERIES/2018/DEC/SWG-PEL/38.

- 1195 De Decker, A., 1973. Agulhas Bank plankton. In: The Biology of the Indian Ocean.
1196 Zeitschel, B. (Ed). Springer, Berlin, 189-219.
- 1197 De Decker, A.H.B., 1984. Near-surface copepod distribution in the south-western Indian and
1198 south-eastern Atlantic Ocean. Ann. S. Afr. Mus. 93(5), 303-370.
- 1199 De Decker, A.H.B., Kaczmaruk, B.Z., Marska, G., 1991. A new species of *Calanus*
1200 (Copepoda, Calanoida) from South African waters. Ann. S. Afr. Mus. 101, 27-44.
- 1201 De Decker, A.H.B., Mombeck, F.J., 1964. South African contribution to the International
1202 Indian Ocean Expedition. 4. A preliminary report on the planktonic copepoda. Investl
1203 Rep. Div. Sea Fish. 51, 10-67.
- 1204 Fields, D.M., 2015. The feeding behavior of *Pleuromamma xiphias* (Calanoida:
1205 Metridinidae): A vertically migrating copepod. PhD thesis, Georgia Institute of
1206 Technology, 48 pp. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.5097.5443>
- 1207 Gallienne, C.P., Robins, D.B., 2001. Is *Oithona* the most important copepod in the world's
1208 oceans? J. Plankton. Res. 23,1421-1432.
- 1209 García-Mayoral, E., Roura, Á., Moreno, A., González, Á.F., 2022. Diet composition of wild
1210 *Loligo vulgaris* paralarvae along the West Iberian Peninsula coast. Mar. Ecol. Prog.
1211 Ser. 681, 71-85. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps13915>
- 1212 Gardner, J.L., Peters, A., Kearney, M.R., Joseph, L., Heinsohn, R., 2011. Declining body
1213 size: a third universal response to warming? Trends. Ecol. Evol. 26, 285-291.
1214 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2011.03.005>
- 1215 Gibbons, M.J., 1993. Vertical migration and feeding of *Euphausia lucens* at two 72 h stations
1216 in the southern Benguela upwelling region. Mar. Biol. 116, 257-268.
- 1217 Gibbons, M.J., 1997. Vertical distribution and feeding of *Thalia democratica* on the Agulhas
1218 Bank during March 1994. J. Mar. Biolog. Assoc. U.K. 77, 493-505.
- 1219 Gliwicz, Z.M., 2002. On the different nature of top-down and bottom-up effects in pelagic
1220 food webs. Freshw. Biol. 47, 2296–2312.
- 1221 González, H.E., Smetacek, V., 1994. The possible role of the cyclopoid copepod *Oithona* in
1222 retarding vertical flux of zooplankton faecal material. Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser. 113, 233-
1223 246. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps113233>
- 1224 Haney, JF., 1988. Diel patterns of zooplankton behavior. Bull. Mar. Sci. 43, 583-603.
- 1225 Hatlebakk, M., Graeve, M., Boissonnot, L., Søreide, J.E., 2019. Lipid storage consumption
1226 and feeding ability of *Calanus glacialis* Jaschnov, 1955 males. J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.
1227 521, 151226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2019.151226>

- 1228 Hattori, H., 1989. Bimodal vertical distribution and diel migration of the copepods *Metridia*
1229 *pacifica*, *M. okhotensis* and *Pleuromamma scutullata* in the western North Pacific
1230 Ocean. Mar. Biol. 103, 39-50.
- 1231 Hays, G.C., 2003. A review of the adaptive significance and ecosystem consequences of
1232 zooplankton diel vertical migrations. Hydrobiologia 503, 163–170.
- 1233 Hays, G.C., Warner, A.T., Proctor, C.A., 1995. Spatio-temporal patterns in the diel vertical
1234 migration of the copepod *Metria lucens* in the northeast Atlantic derived from the
1235 Continuous Plankton Recorder survey. Limnol. Oceanogr. 40, 469-475.
- 1236 Hays, G.C., Kennedy, H., Frost, B.W., 2001. Individual variability in diel vertical migration
1237 of a marine copepod: Why some individuals remain at depth when others migrate. .
1238 Limnol. Oceanogr. 46, 2050-2054.
- 1239 Henson S.A., Sarmiento, J.L., Dunne, J.P., Bopp, L., Lima, I., Doney, S.C., John, J.,
1240 Beaulieu, C., 2010. Detection of anthropogenic climate change in satellite records of
1241 ocean chlorophyll and productivity. Biogeosciences 7, 621–640.
1242 <https://doi.org/10.5194/bg-7-621-2010>
- 1243 Höring, F., Cornils, A., Auel, H., Bode, M., Held, C., 2017. Population genetic structure of
1244 *Calanoides natalis* (Copepoda, Calanoida) in the eastern Atlantic Ocean and Benguela
1245 upwelling system, J. Plankton. Res. 39, 618–630. <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/fbx035>
- 1246 Huggett, J.A., 2003. Comparative ecology of the copepods *Calanoides carinatus* and *Calanus*
1247 *agulhensis* in the southern Benguela and Agulhas Bank ecosystems. Ph.D. thesis,
1248 University of Cape Town: iii + 296 pp.
- 1249 Huggett, J.A., Boyd, A.J., Hutchings, L., Kemp, A.D., 1998. Weekly variability of clupeoid
1250 eggs and larvae in the Benguela jet current: implications for recruitment. In: Benguela
1251 Dynamics. Impacts of variability on shelf-sea environments and their living resources.
1252 Pillar, S. C., Moloney, C. L., Payne, A. I. L. and F. A. Shillington (Eds.) S. Afr. J. mar.
1253 Sci. 19, 197-210.
- 1254 Huggett, J.A., Richardson, A.J., 2000. A review of the biology and ecology of *Calanus*
1255 *agulhensis* off South Africa. ICES Mar. Sci. Symp. 57, 1834-1849.
- 1256 Huggett, J.A., Richardson, A.J., Field, J.G. 2007. Comparative ecology of the copepods
1257 *Calanoides carinatus* and *Calanus agulhensis* – the influence of temperature and food.
1258 Afr. J. Mar. Sci., 29, 473–490. <https://doi.org/10.2989/AJMS.2007.29.3.14.344>
- 1259 Huggett, J.A., Verheye, H.M., Escribano, R., Fairweather, T., 2009. Copepod biomass, size
1260 composition and production in the Southern Benguela: spatio-temporal patterns of
1261 variation, and comparison with other eastern boundary upwelling systems. Prog.
1262 Oceanogr. 83, 197-207.

- 1263 Hutchings, L., 1994. The Agulhas Bank: a synthesis of available information and a brief
1264 comparison with other east-coast shelf regions. *S. Afr. J. Sci.* 90, 179-185.
- 1265 Hutchings, L., Verheye, H.M., Mitchell-Innes, B.A., Peterson, W.T., Huggett, J.A., Painting
1266 S.J., 1995. Copepod production in the southern Benguela system. *ICES Mar. Sci.*
1267 *Symp.* 52, 439-455.
- 1268 Hutchings, L., Beckley, L.E., Griffiths, M.H., Roberts, M.J., Sundby, S., van der Lingen, C.,
1269 2002. Spawning on the edge: spawning grounds and nursery areas around the southern
1270 African coastline. *Mar. Freshwater Res.*, 53, 307–318.
- 1271 Jackson, J.M., Rainville, L., Roberts, M.J, McQuaid, C.D., Lutjeharms, J.R.E., 2012.
1272 Mesoscale bio-physical interactions between the Agulhas Current and the Agulhas
1273 Bank, South Africa. *Cont. Shelf Res.* 49, 10–24.
- 1274 Jacobs, Z., Roberts, M., Jebri, F., Srokosz, M., Kelly, S., Sauer, W., Bruggeman, J., Popova,
1275 E., This issue. Drivers of productivity on the Agulhas Bank and the importance for
1276 marine ecosystems. *Deep sea Res. Part II top. Stud. Oceanogr.*
- 1277 James, A.G. 1987. Feeding ecology, diet and field-based studies on feeding selectivity of the
1278 Cape anchovy *Engraulis capensis* Gilchrist. In: *The Benguela and Comparable*
1279 *Ecosystems*. Payne, A.I.L., Gulland, J.A. and K.H. Brink (Eds). *S. Afr. J. mar. Sci.* 5,
1280 673-692.
- 1281 James, A.G., Findlay, K.P., 1989. Effect of particle size and concentration on feeding
1282 behaviour, selectivity and rates of food ingestion by the Cape anchovy *Engraulis*
1283 *capensis*. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 50, 275-294.
- 1284 Kiørboe, T., 2011. How zooplankton feed: mechanisms, traits and trade-offs. *Biol. Rev.* 86,
1285 311–339. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-185X.2010.00148.x
- 1286 Kiørboe, T., Hirst, A.G., 2014. Shifts in mass scaling of respiration, feeding, and growth rates
1287 across life-form transitions in marine pelagic organisms. *Am. Nat.* 183, E118–E130.
- 1288 Lamont, T., Barlow, R.G., Brewin, R.J.W., 2019. Long-term trends in phytoplankton
1289 chlorophyll *a* and size structure in the Benguela Upwelling System. *J. Geophys. Res.*
1290 *Oceans*, 124, 1170–1195. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JC014334>
- 1291 Largier, J.L., Swart, V.P., 1987. East-west variation in thermocline breakdown on the
1292 Agulhas Bank. In *The Benguela and Comparable Ecosystems*. Payne, A.D.L., Gulland,
1293 J.A., Brink, K.H., (eds) *S. Afr. J. Mar. Sci.* 5, 263–272.
- 1294 Largier, J.L., Chapman, P., Peterson, W.T., Swart, V.P., 1992. The western Agulhas Bank:
1295 circulation, stratification and ecology. In *Benguela Trophic Functioning*. Payne, A. I.
1296 L., Brink, K. H., Mann, K. H., Hilborn, R. (eds). *S. Afr. J. mar. Sci.* 12, 319-339.
- 1297 Lenz, P.H. 2012. The biogeography and ecology of myelin in marine copepods. *J. Plankton.*
1298 *Res.* 34, 575–589.

- 1299 Lenz, P.H., Hartline, D.K., Davis, A.D., 2000. The need for speed. I. Fast reactions and
1300 myelinated axons in copepods. *J. Comp. Physiol. A Sens. Neural Behav. Physiol.*, 186,
1301 337–345.
- 1302 Litchman, E., Ohman, M.D., Kiørboe, T., 2013. Trait-based approaches to zooplankton
1303 communities. *J. Plankton Res.* 35, 473–484. doi:10.1093/plankt/fbt019
- 1304 Liu, H., Hopcroft, R.R., 2006. Growth and development of *Metridia pacifica* (Copepoda:
1305 Calanoida) in the northern Gulf of Alaska. *J. Plankton Res.* 28, 769–781.
- 1306 Longhurst, A., Williams, R., 1979. Materials for plankton modelling: Vertical distribution of
1307 Atlantic zooplankton in summer. *J. Plankton Res.*, 1, 1–28.
1308 <https://doi.org/10.1093/plankt/1.1.1>
- 1309 Lonsdale, D.J., Caron, D.A., Dennett, M.R., Schaffner, R., 2000. Predation by *Oithona* spp.
1310 on protozooplankton in the Ross Sea, Antarctica. *Deep sea Res. Part II top. Stud.*
1311 *Oceanogr.* 47, 3273-3283.
- 1312 Lutjeharms, J.R.E., 2006. The Coastal Oceans of South-Eastern Africa. In: *The global*
1313 *Coastal Ocean: Multiscale Interdisciplinary Process*. Robinson, A.R., Brink, K.H. (eds).
1314 *The Sea*, vol. 14, 781–832.
- 1315 Lutjeharms, J.R.E., 2007. Three decades of research on the greater Agulhas Current. *Ocean*
1316 *Science*, 3, pp. 129-147.
- 1317 Lutjeharms, J.R.E., Catzel, R., Valentine, H.R., 1989. Eddies and other boundary phenomena
1318 of the Agulhas Current. *Cont. Shelf Res.* 9, 597-616.
- 1319 Lutjeharms, J.R.E., Penven, P., Roy, C., 2003. Modelling the shear edge eddies of the
1320 southern Agulhas Current. *Cont. Shelf Res.* 23, 1099–1115.
- 1321 Mazwane, S.L., Poulton, A.J., Hickman, A., Jebri, F., Jacobs Z., Roberts, M., Noyon, M. This
1322 issue. Seasonal and long-term stability of Net Primary Production on the Agulhas Bank,
1323 1998 - 2018. *Deep sea Res. Part II top. Stud. Oceanogr.*
- 1324 McGinty, N., Barton, A.D., Record, N.R., Finkel, Z.V., Irwin, A.J., 2018. Traits structure
1325 copepod niches in the North Atlantic and Southern Ocean. *Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser.* 601,
1326 109-126. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps12660>
- 1327 Mitchell-Innes, B.A. Richardson, A.J., Painting, S.J., 1999. Seasonal changes in
1328 phytoplankton biomass on the western Agulhas Bank, South Africa. *S. Afr. J. mar. Sci.*
1329 21, 217–233.
- 1330 Nishibe, Y., Kobari, T., Ota, T., 2010. Feeding by the cyclopoid copepod *Oithona similis* on
1331 the microplankton assemblage in the Oyashio region during spring. *Plankton Benthos*
1332 *Res.* 5, 74–78.

- 1333 Noyon, M., Poulton, A.J., Asdar, S., Weitz, R., Giering, S.L., this issue. Zooplankton
 1334 community structure on the 1029 Agulhas Bank in autumn: size structure and growth.
 1335 Deep sea Res. Part II top. Stud. Oceanogr.
- 1336 Ohman, M.D., Romagnan, J-B., 2016. Nonlinear effects of body size and optical attenuation
 1337 on Diel Vertical Migration by zooplankton. Limnol. Oceanogr. 61, 2016, 765–770
- 1338 Ohtsuka, S., Okada, M., Kubo, N., Gushima, K., 1993. Attachment and feeding of pelagic
 1339 copepods on larvacean houses. J. Oceanogr. Soc. Japan 48, 115-120.
- 1340 Oksanen, J., Blanchet, F.G., Friendly, M., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., McGlinn, D., Minchin,
 1341 P.R., O’Hara, R.B., Simpson, G.L., Solymos, P., Stevens, M.H.H., Szoecs, E., Wagner,
 1342 H., 2020. Vegan: community ecology package. R Package Version 2. 5–7.
 1343 <https://cran.r-project.org>, <https://github.com/vegandevs/vegan>
- 1344 Osgood, K.E., Frost, B.W., 1994. Ontogenetic diel vertical migration behaviors of the
 1345 plankton copepods *Calanus pacificus* and *Metridia lucens*. Mar. Ecol. Prog. Ser. 104,
 1346 13-15.
- 1347 Paffenhöfer, G-A., 1993. On the ecology of marine cyclopoid copepods (Crustacea,
 1348 Copepoda). J. Plankton. Res. 15, 37-55.
- 1349 Penven, P., Lutjeharms, J.R.E., Marchesiello, P., Roy, C., Weeks, S.J., 2001. Generation of
 1350 cyclonic eddies by the Agulhas Current in the lee of the Agulhas Bank. Geophys. Res.
 1351 Lett. 27, 1055-1058.
- 1352 Peterson, W.T., 1998. Life cycle strategies of copepods in coastal upwelling zones. J. Mar.
 1353 Syst. 15, 313–326.
- 1354 Peterson, W.T., Hutchings, L., 1995. Distribution, abundance and production of *Calanus*
 1355 *agulhensis* on the Agulhas Bank in relation to spatial variations in hydrography and
 1356 chlorophyll. J. Plankton. Res. 17, 2275-2294
- 1357 Peterson, W.T., Hutchings, L., Huggett, J.A., Largier, J.L., 1992. Anchovy spawning in
 1358 relation to the biomass and the replenishment rate of their copepod prey on the western
 1359 Agulhas Bank. In Benguela Trophic Functioning, eds. A.I.L. Payne et al. S. Afr. J. Mar.
 1360 Sci. 12, 487-500.
- 1361 Peterson, W.T., Painting, S.J., Hutchings, L., 1990. Diel variations in gut pigment content,
 1362 diel vertical migration and estimates of grazing impact for copepods in the southern
 1363 Benguela upwelling region in October 1987. J. Plankton. Res. 12, 259-281.
- 1364 Pillar SC. 1984. Diel variation in the vertical distribution of some common zooplankton
 1365 species off the west coast of South Africa. S. Afr. J. mar. Sci. 2, 71-80. DOI:
 1366 10.2989/02577618409504360
- 1367 Piontkovski, S.A., Al-Mawali, A., Al-Kharusi, A., Al-Manthri, W. M., Smith, S., & Popova,
 1368 E. (2015). Mesozooplankton of the Omani shelf: taxonomy, seasonality, and spatial

- 1369 distribution. International Aquatic Research 7, 301-314.
1370 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40071-015-0114-x>
- 1371 Porri, F., McQuaid, C.D., Froneman, W.P., 2007. Spatio-temporal variability of small
1372 copepods (especially *Oithona plumifera*) in shallow nearshore waters off the south
1373 coast of South Africa. Estuar. Coast. Shelf Sci. 72, 711-720.
1374 doi:10.1016/j.ecss.2006.12.006
- 1375 Poulton, A.J., Mazwane, S.L., Godfrey, B., Carvalho, A., Mawji, E., Wihsgott, J.U., Noyon,
1376 M., This issue. Primary production dynamics on the Agulhas Bank in autumn (March
1377 2019). Deep sea Res. Part II top. Stud. Oceanogr.
- 1378 Probyn, T.A., Mitchell-Innes, B.A., Brown, P.C., Hutchings, L., Carter, R.A. 1994. A review
1379 of primary production and related processes on the Agulhas Bank. S. Afr. J. Sci. 90,
1380 166-173.
- 1381 Razouls, C., Desreumaux, N., Kouwenberg, J., de Bovée F., 2005-2022. Biodiversity of
1382 Marine Planktonic Copepods (morphology, geographical distribution and biological
1383 data). Sorbonne University, CNRS. Available at <http://copepodes.obs-banyuls.fr/en>
1384 [Accessed October 26, 2022]
- 1385 Richardson, A.J., 2008. In hot water: zooplankton and climate change. ICES Mar. Sci.
1386 Symp. 65, 279–295.
- 1387 Richardson, A.J., Verheye, H.M., 1998. The relative importance of food and temperature to
1388 copepod egg production and somatic growth in the southern Benguela upwelling
1389 system. J. Plankt. Res. 20, 2379-2399.
- 1390 Richardson, A.J., Verheye, H.M., 1999. Growth rates of copepods in the southern Benguela
1391 upwelling system: The interplay between body size and food. Limnol. Oceanogr. 44,
1392 383-392.
- 1393 Roberts, M.J., 2005. Chokka squid (*Loligo vulgaris reynaudii*) abundance linked to changes
1394 in South Africa's Agulhas Bank ecosystem during spawning and the early life cycle.
1395 ICES Mar. Sci. Symp. 62, 33-55. doi:10.1016/j.icesjms.2004.10.002
- 1396 Roy, C., van der Lingen, C.D., Coetzee, J.C., Lutjeharms, J.R.E., 2007. Abrupt
1397 environmental shift associated with changes in the distribution of Cape anchovy
1398 *Engraulis encrasicolus* spawners in the southern Benguela. Afr. J. Mar. Sci. 29(3),
1399 309–319. <https://doi.org/10.2989/AJMS.2007.29.3.1.331>
- 1400 Sabatini, M.E., Ramírez, F.C., Bradford-Grieve, J., 2007. Redescription of *Calanoides*
1401 *carinatus* (Krøyer) (Copepoda:Calanoida:Calanidae) with a discussion on the status of
1402 related species. Invertebrate Systematics, 21, 341–364. <https://doi.org/10.1071/IS06050>
- 1403 Saraswathy, M., Krishnaiyer, H., 1986. Ecology of *Pleuromamma indica* Wolfenden
1404 (Copepoda-Calanoida) in the Indian Ocean. Indian J. Mar. Sci. 15, 219-222.

- 1405 Schminke, H.K., 2007. Entomology for the copepodologist. J. Plankton. Res. 29, i149–i162.
1406 <https://doi.org.10.1093/plankt/fbl073>
- 1407 Shannon, L.V., Pillar, S.C., 1986. The Benguela Ecosystem Part III. Plankton. Oceanogr.
1408 Mar. Biol. Ann. Rev. 24: 65-170.
- 1409 Shelton, P.A., Hutchings, L., 1982. Transport of anchovy, *Engraulis capensis* Gilchrist, eggs
1410 and early larvae by a frontal jet current. J. Cons. int. Explor. Mer. 40: 185-198.
- 1411 Shelton, P.A., Hutchings, L., 1990. Ocean stability and anchovy spawning in the southern
1412 Benguela Current region. Fish. Bull. 88, 323-338.
- 1413 Smith, S.L., 1982. The northwestern Indian Ocean during the monsoons of 1979:
1414 Distribution, abundance and feeding of zooplankton. Deep-Sea Res. 29, 1331–1353.
- 1415 Smith, S.L., Madhupratap, M., 2005. Mesozooplankton of the Arabian Sea: Patterns
1416 influenced by seasons, upwelling, and oxygen concentrations. Prog. Oceanogr. 65, 214-
1417 239.
- 1418 Sun, R.X., Wang, Y.G., Wang, C.G., Xiang, P., Chen, X.Y., Xing, B.P., 2022. Research
1419 advance in the taxonomy and ecology of Oncaeidae Giesbrecht, 1893. Front. Mar. Sci.
1420 9, 919877. <https://doi.org.10.3389/fmars.2022.919877>
- 1421 Swart, V.P., Largier, J., 1987. Thermal structure of Agulhas Bank water. In: The Benguela
1422 and Comparable Ecosystems. Payne, A.I.L., Gulland, J.A., Brink, K.H., (Eds). S. Afr. J.
1423 mar. Sci. 5, 243-253.
- 1424 Sweijid, N.A., Smit, A.J., 2020. Trends in sea surface temperature and chlorophyll-*a* in the
1425 seven African Large Marine Ecosystems. Environ. Dev. 36, 100585.
1426 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2020.100585>
- 1427 Teuber, L., Schukat, A., Hagen, W., Auel, H., 2014. Trophic interactions and life strategies of
1428 epi- to bathypelagic calanoid copepods of the tropical Atlantic Ocean. J. Plankton. Res.
1429 36, 1109-1123.
- 1430 Timonin, A.G., Arashkevich, E.G., Drits, A.V., Semenova, T.N., 1992. Zooplankton
1431 dynamics in the northern Benguela ecosystem, with special reference to the copepod
1432 *Calanoides carinatus*. S. Afr. J. mar. Sci. 12, 545-560.
1433 DOI:10.2989/02577619209504724
- 1434 Turner, J.T., 2004. The importance of small planktonic copepods and their roles in pelagic
1435 marine food webs. Zool. Stud. 43, 255-266.
- 1436 van der Lingen, C.D., 2002. Diet of sardine *Sardinops sagax* in the southern Benguela
1437 upwelling ecosystem. S. Afr. J. mar. Sci. 24, 301–316.
- 1438 van der Lingen, C.D., Bertrand, A., Bode, A., Brodeur, R., Cubillos, L.A., Espinoza, P.,
1439 Friedland, K., Garrido, S., Irigoien, X., Miller, T., Möllmann, C., Rodriguez-Sanchez,

- 1440 R., Tanaka, H., Temming, A., Chapter 7. Trophic dynamics. In: Checkley, D., Alheit,
1441 J., Oozeki, Y., & Roy, C., eds. 2009. Climate Change and Small Pelagic Fish.
1442 Cambridge University Press.
- 1443 van der Lingen, C.D., Hampton, I., 2018. Chapter 11. Climate change impacts, vulnerabilities
1444 and adaptations: Southeast Atlantic and Southwest Indian Ocean marine fisheries. In:
1445 Barange, M., Bahri, T., Beveridge, M.C.M., Cochrane, K.L., Funge-Smith, S. &
1446 Poulain, F., eds. 2018. Impacts of climate change on fisheries and aquaculture:
1447 synthesis of current knowledge, adaptation and mitigation options. FAO Fisheries and
1448 Aquaculture Technical Paper No. 627. Rome, FAO.
- 1449 van der Lingen, C., Huggett, J.A., 2003. The role of ichthyoplankton surveys in recruitment
1450 research and management of South African anchovy and sardine. In: The Big Fish
1451 Bang – Proceedings of the 26th Annual Larval Fish Conference. Browman, H.I. and A.
1452 B. Skiftesvik (Eds). Institute of Marine Research, Bergen, p. 303-343.
- 1453 van der Lingen, C.D., Shannon, L.J., Cury, P.M., Kreiner, A., Moloney, C.L., Roux, J., Vaz-
1454 Velho, F., 2006. Resource and ecosystem variability, including regime shifts in the
1455 Benguela Current system. In: Shannon, L.V., Hempel, G., Malanotte Rizzoli, P.,
1456 Moloney, C.L., Woods, J. (Eds.), Benguela: Predicting a Large Marine Ecosystem, pp.
1457 147–184.
- 1458 Verheye, H.M., 2000. Decadal-scale trends across several marine trophic levels in the
1459 southern Benguela upwelling system off South Africa. *Ambio* 29: 30-34.
- 1460 Verheye, H.M., Field, J.G., 1992, Vertical distribution and diel vertical migration of
1461 *Calanoides carinatus* (Kroyer, 1849) development stages in the Southern Benguela
1462 upwelling region. *J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol.*, 158, 123-140. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0981(92)90312-X)
1463 [0981\(92\)90312-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0981(92)90312-X)
- 1464 Verheye, H.M., Hutchings, L., Huggett, J.A., Carter, R.A., Peterson, W.T., Painting, S.J.,
1465 1994. Community structure, distribution and trophic ecology of zooplankton on the
1466 Agulhas Bank with special reference to copepods. *S. Afr. J. Sci.* 90, 154-165.
- 1467 Verheye, H.M., Hutchings, L., Huggett, J.A., Painting, S.J., 1992. Mesozooplankton
1468 dynamics in the Benguela ecosystem, with emphasis on the herbivorous copepods. *S.*
1469 *Afr. J. Mar. Sci.* 12, 561-584. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2989/02577619209504725>
- 1470 Verheye, H.M., Hutchings, L., Peterson, W.T., 1991. Life history and population
1471 maintenance strategies of *Calanoides carinatus* (Copepoda: Calanoida) in the southern
1472 Benguela ecosystem. *S. Afr. J. mar. Sci.* 11, 179-191.
- 1473 Verheye, H.M, Richardson, A.J., Hutchings, H., Marska, G., Gianakouras, D., 1998. Long-
1474 term trends in the abundance and community structure of coastal zooplankton in the
1475 southern Benguela system, 1951–1996. In: Benguela Dynamics, Pillar, S. C., Moloney,
1476 C. L., Payne, A. I. L. and F. A. Shillington (Eds). *S. Afr. J. mar. Sci.* 19: 317–332.

- 1477 Viñas, M.D., Blanco-Bercial, L., Bucklin, A., Verheye, H., Guilherme, J., Bersano, F.,
1478 Ceballos, S., 2015. Phylogeography of the copepod *Calanoides carinatus s.l.* (Krøyer)
1479 reveals cryptic species and delimits *C. carinatus s.s.* distribution in SW Atlantic Ocean.
1480 J. Exp. Mar. Biol. Ecol., 468, 97–104. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jembe.2015.03.012>
- 1481 Violle, C., Navas, M.-L., Vile, D., Kazakou, E., Fortunel, C., Hummel, I., Garnier, E., 2007.
1482 Let the concept of trait be functional! Oikos 116, 882-892.
- 1483 Walker, N.D., 1986. Satellite observations of the Agulhas Current and episodic upwelling
1484 south of Africa. Deep Sea Res. 33, 1083-1106.
- 1485 Wallace-Fincham, B.P., 1987. The food and feeding of *Etrumeus whiteheadi* Wongratana
1486 1983 off the Cape Province of South Africa. M.Sc. thesis, University of Cape Town,
1487 117 pp.
- 1488 Walter, T.C., Boxshall, G., 2020. World of Copepods database. Accessed at
1489 <http://www.marinespecies.org/copepoda> on 2020-10-01. doi:10.14284/356
- 1490 Wang, L., Du, F., Wang, X., Li, Y., Ning, J., 2017. Distribution and role of the genus
1491 *Oithona* (Copepoda: Cyclopoida) in the South China Sea. Oceanologia 59, 300-310.
1492 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.oceano.2017.03.009>
- 1493 Yamaguchi, R., Suga, T., 2019. Trend and variability in global upper-ocean stratification
1494 since the 1960s. J. Geophys. Res. Oceans, 124(12), 8933–8948.
1495 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JC015439>
- 1496 Yang, H., Lohmann, G., Wei, W., Dima, M., Ionita, M., Liu, J., 2016. Intensification and
1497 poleward shift of subtropical western boundary currents in a warming climate, J.
1498 Geophys. Res. Oceans, 121, 4928–4945. doi:10.1002/2015JC011513.
- 1499 Zamora-Terol, S., McKinnon, A.D., Saiz, E., 2014. Feeding and egg production of *Oithona*
1500 spp. in tropical waters of North Queensland, Australia. J. Plankton Res. 36:1047–1059.
1501 doi:10.1093/plankt/fbu039.
- 1502
- 1503

1504 **List of Tables**

1505 **Table 1:** Spatially integrated means for environmental variables during November-December
1506 1988-2011 for the Western Agulhas Bank (WAB), Central Agulhas Bank (CAB) and Eastern
1507 Agulhas Bank (EAB) as well as for the whole Agulhas Bank. The standard deviation,
1508 representing the interannual variability, is provided in brackets, and $n = 24$ for all areas.

1509 **Table 2:** Mean annual biomass (mg C m^{-2}) and abundance (no m^{-2}) of the dominant copepod
1510 taxa during November-December over the whole Agulhas Bank, and proportion of total
1511 copepod biomass and abundance. The standard deviation, representing the interannual
1512 variability, is provided in brackets; $n = 24$.

1513 **Table 3:** Functional traits for common Agulhas Bank copepod taxa.

1514 **Table 4:** Results of linear regression analysis (r^2 values and significance) between annual
1515 acoustic estimates of pelagic fish biomass (anchovy *Engraulis encrasicolus*, sardine
1516 *Sardinops sagax* and redeye round herring *Etrumeus whiteheadi*, and total pelagic fish
1517 biomass; DAFF, 2018) and annual copepod biomass estimates (total copepod, *C. agulhensis*
1518 and small calanoid biomass) from the GAM during the November surveys. * indicates $p <$
1519 0.05 , ** indicates $p < 0.01$, *** indicates $p < 0.001$, ns = not significant.

1520

1521

1522 **List of Figures**

1523 **Figure 1:** Schematic of circulatory features influencing the Agulhas Bank, including near-
1524 surface currents over the continental shelf, and the strong-flowing Agulhas Current (1-3 m s-
1525 ¹). The darker blue shaded areas indicate main upwelling areas, and the lighter blue shaded
1526 area indicates the approximate location of the cold ridge. Adapted from Boyd et al. (1992),
1527 Hutchings (1994) and Lutjeharms (2006). Dashed lines separate the western (WAB), central
1528 (CAB) and eastern Agulhas Bank (EAB) as applied in this study. Port Elizabeth is now
1529 Gqeberha.

1530 **Figure 2:** (a) Estimated mean temperature (°C) at the surface (5 m; SST) and (b) a depth of
1531 30 m, (c) the temperature difference between 5 and 30 m, estimated mean chlorophyll a (d) at
1532 the surface (5 m) and (e) at a depth of 30 m (mg m⁻³), and (f) integrated chlorophyll a in the
1533 upper 100 m (mg m⁻²). The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths.
1534 Abbreviations: CT = Cape Town, CA = Cape Agulhas, MB = Mossel Bay, PB = Plettenberg
1535 Bay, PE = Port Elizabeth (now Gqeberha), PA = Port Alfred.

1536 **Figure 3:** Estimated mean (a) total copepod abundance (No. m⁻²) and (b) total copepod
1537 biomass (mg C m⁻²) on the Agulhas Bank during November-December from 1988 to 2011.
1538 The solid white line indicates the mean 17°C isotherm at a depth of 30 m, and the dashed
1539 green line indicates the mean 0.9 mg m⁻³ chlorophyll a isoline at 30 m. The grey lines
1540 correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

1541 **Figure 4:** Estimated mean biomass (mg C m⁻²) of dominant copepod taxa on the Agulhas
1542 Bank during November-December, from 1988 to 2011, in decreasing order of biomass: (a)
1543 *Calanus agulhensis*, (b) small Calanoida (mainly Paracalanidae & Clausocalanidae), (c)
1544 *Metridia lucens*, (d) *Calanoides natalis*, (e) *Centropages* spp., (f) Oncaeidae, (g)
1545 *Pleuromamma* spp., (h) Oithonidae. Note the difference in scales. Line drawings of female
1546 copepods (dorsal view) from Razouls et al. (2005-2020). Mean total length ranges from 3.22
1547 mm for *Pleuromamma* spp to 0.79 mm for the Oithonidae (not to scale). The solid white line
1548 represents the mean 17°C isotherm at a depth of 30 m, and the dashed green line indicates the
1549 mean 0.9 mg m⁻³ chlorophyll a isoline at 30 m. The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200
1550 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

1551 **Figure 5:** Centre of gravity of upper 10% of highest biomass values for (a) the dominant
1552 copepod taxa and (b) the developmental stages of *Calanus agulhensis* during November-
1553 December 1988 to 2011 (each dot represents one survey). The grey lines correspond to the
1554 100 and 200 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

1555 **Figure 6:** Distribution of estimated mean biomass (mg C m⁻²) of (a) large calanoid nauplii,
1556 (b-f) copepodite stages C1 to C5, and (g) female and (h) male adult stages of *Calanus*
1557 *agulhensis* over the Agulhas Bank during November-December from 1988 to 2011. Note the
1558 difference in scales. Line drawings indicate relative size of the different developmental
1559 stages, ranging from a mean total length of ~0.50-0.75 mm for late-stage *C. agulhensis*
1560 nauplii to 2.76 mm for *C. agulhensis* females. The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200

1561 m isobaths. The solid white line represents the mean 17°C isotherm at a depth of 30 m, and
1562 the dashed green line indicates the mean 0.9 mg m⁻³ chl *a* isoline at 30 m. For abbreviations
1563 see Fig. 2.

1564 **Figure 7:** Interannual variability in (a) mean temperature (°C) at the surface (5m), at 30 m
1565 and at the depth of the 17°C isotherm; (b) area (squares, km²) and volume (vol, circles, km³)
1566 of upwelled water (defined as less than 17°C within the upper 30 m) for the coastal upwelling
1567 (CU, <50m bottom depth) and cold ridge (CR, 50-200 m bottom depth) regions on the CAB
1568 and EAB combined; (c) mean chlorophyll *a* (mg m⁻³) at 5 m and 30 m, and integrated
1569 chlorophyll *a* (mg m⁻²) within the upper 100 m. Data are averages during late spring (Oct-
1570 Dec) across all years (1988-2011) for temperature (see Fig. 8) and all years except 1999 and
1571 2001 for chlorophyll *a* (see Fig. S13).

1572 **Figure 8:** Estimated temperature (°C) at 30 m during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to
1573 2011. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

1574 **Figure 9:** Time-series of estimated mean total copepod biomass (mg C m⁻²) over the entire
1575 Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988-2011, and for the western (WAB),
1576 central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors. All regions showed significant negative linear
1577 trends; exponential (best) fit shown for entire bank.

1578 **Figure 10:** Estimated total copepod biomass (mg C m⁻²) over the Agulhas Bank during late
1579 spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

1580 **Figure 11:** Time-series of estimated mean biomass (mg C m⁻²) of copepod taxa (a) *Calanus*
1581 *agulhensis*, (b) *Calanoides natalis*, (c) *Centropages* spp., (d) *Metridia lucens*, (e) *Oithonidae*,
1582 (f) *Oncaeidae*, (g) *Pleuromamma* spp., (h) small calanoids (Paracalanidae and
1583 Clausocalanidae) over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB)
1584 and eastern (EAB) sectors, during late spring (Oct-Dec) 1988-2011. Exponential (best) fits
1585 shown for the entire bank, where significant linear trends were found. Note the different y-
1586 axis scales.

1587 **Figure 12:** Time series of estimated mean biomass (mg C m⁻³) of *C. agulhensis* (a) all stages,
1588 (b) females, (c) males, (d) C5s, (e) C4s, (f) all C1-C3 juveniles, (g) C3s, (h) C2s, (i) C1s, and
1589 (j) large copepod nauplii over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central
1590 (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors, during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011.
1591 Exponential (best) fits shown for the entire bank, where significant linear trends were found.
1592 Note the different y-axis scales.

1593 **Figure 13:** Ordination of the copepod community of the Agulhas Bank according to the year
1594 (label) and the region of the bank (colours, EAB, CAB, WAB). The ordination is based on a
1595 non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS, stress = 0.17) of the average biomass (from the
1596 GAM model) over each area. The left-hand panel represents the years/regions and the right
1597 panel the species/stages (Cal: *Calanus agulhensis*, Oides: *Calanoides natalis*, Oith:
1598 *Oithonidae*, Onc.: *Oncaeidae*, Metrid: *Metridia lucens*, Centrop.: *Centropages* spp, Pleuro.:

1599 *Pleuromma* spp., SmCal: small calanoids (Para- and Clausocalanidae), M: male, F: female, 5
1600 and 4: copepodites stage 5 and 4, Juv: juveniles).

1601 **Figure 14:** Time-series of, and significant linear regressions between, mean annual (a, b)
1602 total copepod biomass (mg C m^{-2}) and total pelagic fish biomass (10^3 tons), (c, d) *C.*
1603 *agulhensis* biomass and anchovy biomass, and (e, f) *C. agulhensis* biomass and redeye
1604 biomass over the entire Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988-2011 (shown
1605 from 1986 onwards for the fish).

1606

1607 **Table 1:** Spatially integrated means for environmental variables during November-
 1608 December 1988-2011 for the Western Agulhas Bank (WAB), Central Agulhas Bank (CAB)
 1609 and Eastern Agulhas Bank (EAB) as well as for the whole Agulhas Bank. The standard
 1610 deviation, representing the interannual variability, is provided in brackets, and $n = 24$ for all
 1611 areas.

1612

Area	Surface temperature (°C)	Temperature at 30 m (°C)	Depth of 17°C isotherm (m)	Surface Chl <i>a</i> (mg m ⁻³)	Chl <i>a</i> at 30 m (mg m ⁻³)	Integrated Chl <i>a</i> in upper 100 m (mg m ⁻²)
WAB	18.00 (0.77)	17.33 (0.70)	40.66 (9.07)	0.94 (0.27)	0.95 (0.27)	52.80 (12.39)
CAB	19.05 (0.75)	18.05 (0.71)	46.84 (8.16)	0.79 (0.24)	0.95 (0.27)	49.42 (13.27)
EAB	18.91 (0.97)	16.23 (1.02)	28.26 (6.59)	1.27 (0.45)	0.98 (0.25)	55.11 (13.69)
Whole bank	18.82 (0.75)	17.32 (0.72)	39.59 (6.94)	0.98 (0.26)	0.96 (0.22)	51.90 (11.00)

1613

1614

1615 **Table 2:** Mean annual biomass (mg C m⁻²) and abundance (no m⁻²) of the dominant copepod
 1616 taxa during November-December over the whole Agulhas Bank, and proportion of total
 1617 copepod biomass and abundance. The standard deviation, representing the interannual
 1618 variability, is provided in brackets; n = 24.

1619

Taxon	Biomass (mg C m ⁻²)	% Total Biomass	Abundance (no m ⁻²)	% Total Abundance
<i>Calanus agulhensis</i>	512.6 (423.7)	50.0	27,101 (23,184)	17.1
Small calanoids*	233.2 (75.3)	22.7	58,279 (18,793)	36.8
<i>Metridia lucens</i>	75.5 (59.1)	7.4	4,336 (3,516)	2.7
Other copepod taxa [#]	57.6 (23.4)	5.6	3,425 (1,344)	2.2
<i>Calanoides natalis</i>	44.3 (73.7)	4.3	3,337 (6,979)	2.1
<i>Centropages</i> spp.	37.6 (22.7)	3.7	8,156 (4,976)	5.2
Oncaeidae	32.2 (25.8)	3.1	8,038 (6,461)	5.1
<i>Pleuromamma</i> spp.	20.7 (26.9)	2.0	629 (554)	0.4
Large calanoid nauplii	6.3 (3.8)	0.6	15,665 (9,395)	9.9
Oithonidae	5.9 (4.5)	0.6	29,307 (22,266)	18.5
Total	1025,8 (586,2)	100	15,8315 (68,984)	100

1620

1621 * Paracalanidae and Clausocalanidae; [#] includes other large calanoids (e.g., Aetideidae, Candaciidae,
 1622 Eucalanidae, Euchaetidae, Lucicutiidae, *Nannocalanus minor*, Rhincalanidae), other cyclopoids (e.g.,
 1623 Corycaeidae, Sapphirinidae), and harpacticoids.

1624

1625 **Table 3:** Functional traits for common Agulhas Bank copepod taxa.

1626

Taxon	Female Size ^a (TL, mm)	Trophic group	Foraging behaviour	Reproductive mode	Myelination	FG ^b	References
<i>Calanus agulhensis</i>	2.45-2.95	Omnivore-herbivore	Current feeding	Broadcaster	Myelinated	7	Huggett and Richardson (2000), Huggett et al. (2007)
<i>Calanoides natalis</i>	2.20-2.60	Omnivore-herbivore	Current feeding	Broadcaster	Myelinated	7	Verheye and Field (1992), Huggett et al. (2007)
<i>Centropages</i> spp.	1.50-3.00	Omnivore	Mixed (Current/Ambush feeding)	Broadcaster	Myelinated	11	Becker et al. (2021)
<i>Metridia lucens</i>	1.90-4.00	Omnivore	Current feeding	Broadcaster	Amyelinated	3	Becker et al. (2021)
Oithonidae	0.31-1.54	Omnivore	Ambush feeding	Sac-spawner	Amyelinated	10	Becker et al. (2021)
Oncaeidae	0.44-1.70	Detritivore-omnivore	Cruise feeding	Sac-spawner	Amyelinated	2	Becker et al. (2021)
<i>Pleuromamma</i> spp.	2.40-4.50	Omnivore	Current feeding	Broadcaster	Amyelinated	9	Becker et al. (2021)
Clausocalanidae	1.08-1.62	Omnivore-herbivore	Cruise or current feeding	Broadcaster/sac-spawner	Myelinated	1, 7	Becker et al. (2021)
Paracalanidae	0.62-1.30	Omnivore-herbivore	Current feeding	Broadcaster	Myelinated	7	Becker et al. (2021)

1627

1628 ^a Size ranges from Razouls et al. (2005-2022); ^b Functional group (FG) number defined by Benedetti et al. (2022), FG1 = Myelinated cruise-
 1629 feeding herbivores, FG2 = Amyelinated cruise-feeding detritivores, FG3 = Myelinated current/cruise-feeding detritivores, FG7 = Myelinated
 1630 current-feeding herbivores, FG9 = Amyelinated current-feeding omnivores, FG10 = Amyelinated ambush-feeding omnivores, FG11 =
 1631 Amyelinated current-ambush-feeding omnivores/herbivores.

1632 **Table 4:** Results of linear regression analysis (r^2 values and significance) between annual
 1633 acoustic estimates of pelagic fish biomass (anchovy *Engraulis encrasicolus*, sardine
 1634 *Sardinops sagax* and redeye round herring *Etrumeus whiteheadi*, and total pelagic fish
 1635 biomass; DAFF, 2018) and annual copepod biomass estimates (total copepod, *C. agulhensis*
 1636 and small calanoid biomass) from the GAM during the November surveys. * indicates $p <$
 1637 0.05, ** indicates $p < 0.01$, *** indicates $p < 0.001$, ns = not significant.

1638

	Anchovy	Sardine	Redeye	Anchovy + Redeye	Total pelagic fish
Total copepods	0.202 *	ns	0.414 ***	0.316 **	0.255 *
<i>C. agulhensis</i>	0.265 *	ns	0.450 ***	0.390 **	0.325 **
Small calanoids	ns	ns	0.381 **	0.220 *	0.180 *

1639

Figure 1: Schematic of circulatory features influencing the Agulhas Bank, including near-surface currents over the continental shelf, and the strong-flowing Agulhas Current ($1-3 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). The darker blue shaded areas indicate main upwelling areas, and the lighter blue shaded area indicates the approximate location of the cold ridge. Adapted from Boyd et al. (1992), Hutchings (1994) and Lutjeharms (2006). Dashed lines separate the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern Agulhas Bank (EAB) as applied in this study. Port Elizabeth is now Gqeberha.

Figure 2: (a) Estimated mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at the surface (5 m; SST) and (b) a depth of 30 m, (c) the temperature difference between 5 and 30 m, (d) estimated mean chlorophyll *a* (d) at the surface (5 m) and (e) a depth of 30 m (mg m^{-3}), and (f) integrated chlorophyll *a* in the upper 100 m (mg m^{-2}). The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths. Abbreviations: CT = Cape Town, CA = Cape Agulhas, MB = Mossel Bay, PB = Plettenberg Bay, PE = Port Elizabeth (now Gqeberha), PA = Port Alfred.

Figure 3: Estimated mean (a) total copepod abundance (No. m^{-2}) and (b) total copepod biomass (mg C m^{-2}) on the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011. The solid white line indicates the mean 17°C isotherm at a depth of 30 m, and the dashed green line indicates the mean 0.9 mg m^{-3} chlorophyll a isoline at 30 m. The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure 4: Estimated mean biomass (mg C m^{-2}) of dominant copepod taxa on the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec), from 1988 to 2011, in decreasing order of biomass: (a) *Calanus agulhensis*, (b) small Calanoida (mainly Paracalanidae & Clausocalanidae), (c) *Metridia lucens*, (d) *Calanoides natalis*, (e) *Centropages* spp., (f) Oncaeidae, (g) *Pleuromamma* spp., (h) Oithonidae. Note the difference in scales. Line drawings of female copepods (dorsal view) from Razouls et al. (2005-2020). Mean total length ranges from 3.22 mm for *Pleuromamma* spp to 0.79 mm for the Oithonidae (not to scale). The solid white line represents the mean 17°C isotherm at a depth of 30 m, and the dashed green line indicates the mean 0.9 mg m^{-3} chlorophyll *a* isoline at 30 m. The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure 5: Centre of gravity of upper 10% of highest biomass values for (a) the dominant copepod taxa and (b) the developmental stages of *Calanus agulhensis* during late spring (Oct-Dec) 1988 to 2011 (each dot represents one survey). The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure 6: Distribution of estimated mean biomass (mg C m^{-2}) of (a) large calanoid nauplii, (b-f) copepodite stages C1 to C5, and (g) female and (h) male adult stages of *Calanus agulhensis* over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011. Note the difference in scales. Line drawings indicate relative size of the different developmental stages, ranging from a mean total length of $\sim 0.50\text{-}0.75$ mm for late-stage *C. agulhensis* nauplii to 2.76 mm for *C. agulhensis* females. The solid white line represents the mean 17°C isotherm at a depth of 30 m, and the dashed green line indicates the mean 0.9 mg m^{-3} chl *a* isoline at 30 m. The grey lines correspond to the 100 and 200 m isobaths. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure 7: Interannual variability in (a) mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at the surface (5m), at 30 m and at the depth of the 17°C isotherm; (b) area (squares, km^2) and volume (vol, circles, km^3) of upwelled water (defined as less than 17°C within the upper 30 m) for the coastal upwelling (CU, <50m bottom depth) and cold ridge (CR, 50-200 m bottom depth) regions on the CAB and EAB combined; (c) mean chlorophyll a (mg m^{-3}) at 5 m and 30 m, and integrated chlorophyll a (mg m^{-2}) within the upper 100 m. Data are averages during late spring (Oct-Dec) across all years (1988-2011) for temperature (see Fig. 8) and all years except 1999 and 2001 for chlorophyll a (see Fig. S13).

Figure 8: Estimated temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at 30 m during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011. For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure 9: Time-series of estimated mean total copepod biomass (mg C m^{-2}) over the entire Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988-2011, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors. All regions showed significant negative linear trends; exponential (best) fit shown for entire bank.

Figure 10: Estimated total copepod biomass (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure 11: Time-series of estimated mean biomass (mg C m^{-2}) of copepod taxa (a) *Calanus agulhensis*, (b) small calanoids (Paracalanidae and Clausocalanidae), (c) *Metridia lucens*, (d) *Calanoides natalis*, (e) *Centropages* spp., (f) *Oncaeidae*, (g) *Pleuromamma* spp. and (h) *Oithonidae*, over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors, during late spring (Oct-Dec), 1988-2011. Exponential (best) fits shown for the entire bank, where significant linear trends were found. Note the different y-axis scales.

Figure 12: Time series of estimated mean biomass (mg C m^{-3}) of (a) large copepod nauplii, and *C. agulhensis* (b) C1s, (c) C2s, (d) C3s, (e) C4s, (f) C5s, (g) females, and (h) males over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors, during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011. Exponential (best) fits shown for the entire bank, where significant linear trends were found. Note the different y-axis scales.

Figure 13: Ordination of the copepod community of the Agulhas Bank according to the year (label) and the region of the bank (colours, EAB, CAB, WAB). The ordination is based on a non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS, stress = 0.17) of the average biomass (from the GAM model) over each area. Panel (a) represents the years/regions and the panel (b) the species/stages (Cal: *Calanus agulhensis*, Oides: *Calanoides natalis*, Oith: Oithonidae, Onc.: Oncaeidae, Metrid: *Metridia lucens*, Centrop.: *Centropages* spp, Pleuro.: *Pleuromamma* spp., SmCal: Small Calanoids, M: male, F: female, 5 and 4: copepodites stage 5 and 4, Juv: juveniles)

Figure 14: Time-series of, and significant linear regressions between, mean annual (a, b) total copepod biomass (mg C m⁻²) and total pelagic fish biomass (10³ tons), (c, d) *C. agulhensis* biomass and anchovy biomass, and (e, f) *C. agulhensis* biomass and redeye biomass over the entire Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988-2011 (shown from 1986 onwards for the fish).

Supplementary data

Figure S1: Map of study area and zooplankton sampling locations on the Agulhas Bank during annual surveys in late austral spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988-2011. Dashed lines delineate the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) regions of the Agulhas Bank. Port Elizabeth is now Gqeberha. Inset indicates number of zooplankton samples analysed from each survey.

Figure S2: Maps of zooplankton sampling locations for each survey conducted in late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011. Abbreviations: CT = Cape Town, CA = Cape Agulhas, MB = Mossel Bay, PB = Plettenberg Bay, PE = Port Elizabeth (now Gqeberha), PA = Port Alfred.

Figure S3: Estimated total biomass of *Calanus agulhensis* (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S4: Estimated total biomass of small calanoid copepods (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S5: Estimated total biomass of *Metridia lucens* (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S6: Estimated total biomass of *Calanoides natalis* (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S7: Estimated total biomass of *Centropages* spp. (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S8: Estimated total biomass of *Oncaeidae* (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S9: Estimated total biomass of *Pleuromamma* spp. (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S10: Estimated total biomass of *Oithonidae* (mg C m^{-2}) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011 (note log scale). For abbreviations see Fig. 2.

Figure S11: Interannual variability in (a) estimated mean temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at the surface (5 m) and (b) a depth of 30 m, (c) the temperature difference between the surface and 30 m, and (d) the depth of the 17°C isotherm (m) over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors, during the surveys in late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011.

Figure S12: Interannual variability in (a) estimated mean chlorophyll *a* (mg m^{-3}) at the surface (5 m) and (b) a depth of 30 m, and (c) integrated chlorophyll *a* in the upper 100 m (mg m^{-2}) over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors, during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011, excluding 1999 and 2001.

Figure S13: Estimated mean integrated chlorophyll *a* (mg m^{-2}) in the upper 100 m during late spring (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011, except for 1999 (due to limited data collected only on the WAB) and 2001 (due to data quality uncertainties). For abbreviations see Fig. S1.

Figure S14: Time series of (a) proportion (%) of total copepod biomass of all *C. agulhensis* stages combined, and proportion of total *C. agulhensis* biomass comprised by (b) females, (c) males, (d) C5s, (e) C4s, (f) all C1-C3 juveniles, (g) C3s, (h) C2s, (i) C1s over the entire Agulhas Bank, and for the western (WAB), central (CAB) and eastern (EAB) sectors, during late spring + (Oct-Dec) from 1988 to 2011.

Figure S15: Time-series of proportion of total copepod biomass comprised by *Calanus agulhensis* and small calanoid copepods (Para- and Clausocalanidae) over the Agulhas Bank during late spring (Oct-Dec) 1988-2011.

